

**AN EVALUATION OF HYPERSPECTRAL AND MULTISPECTRAL
DATA FOR MAPPING INVASIVE SPECIES IN AN AFRICAN
SAVANNA**

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DECLARATION

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As the candidate's supervisor/co-supervisor, I certify that the above declaration is true to the best of my knowledge and have approved this dissertation for submission.

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PUBLICATIONS AND MANUSCRIPTS

The following manuscripts are under peer-review or being prepared for publication. I substantially contributed to the study design, fieldwork, analysis, interpretation and discussion of the results and the overall preparation of the manuscripts, hence I was the appropriate first author in both manuscripts.

Kganyago, M., Odindi, J., Adjorlolo, C. & Mhangara, P. (**Under Review**). Determining optimal spectral subset for discrimination of *Parthenium hysterophorus*: A hierarchical approach using statistical filters and Support Vector Machine - Recursive Feature Elimination wrapper. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*. [Chapter 2]

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An oral presentation titled “Evaluating the Efficacy of Multispectral Remote Sensing for Detecting and Estimating Patch Sizes of *Parthenium Hysterophorus* L. (*Parthenium* Weed) in Kwazulu-Natal, South Africa” was presented by **Kganyago, M.** at 10th Biennial African Association for Remote Sensing of the Environment (AARSE) Conference 2014, University of Johannesburg, South Africa. [Chapter 3]

Signed:

ABSTRACT

Invasive alien plant (IAP) species affects a range of ecosystem types in various regions of the world. Therefore are now considered one of the main phenomena causing global change. Invasive alien plants (IAP's) cause considerable impacts on ecosystem processes and functions, biodiversity, agriculture and human well-being. *Parthenium hysterophorus* is an IAP which is widely spread across the globe. It is difficult to control and eradicate, and has detrimental impacts on the natural environment and human health. However, there is no record of accurate and up-to-date information on the distributions and extent of *P. hysterophorus*. This study evaluated the capability of hyperspectral and multispectral data for mapping *P. hysterophorus* in northern KwaZulu-Natal province, South Africa. First, the study sought to determine an optimal subset of bands from canopy hyperspectral data for discrimination of *P. hysterophorus* from its co-existing species. A novel hierarchical approach that integrates statistical filters and a wrapper technique has been proposed to select optimal bands to solve the problem of high spectral dimensionality and improve classification accuracy. A non-parametric algorithm, Support Vector Machines (SVM) showed inferior classification accuracy, i.e. 76.19% and 78.57% when using 20 best spectral bands from SVM – Recursive Feature Elimination (SVM-RFE) and entire dataset ($n = 1633$), respectively. On the other hand, superior overall accuracy of 83.33% was achieved when using ten spectral bands identified by the hierarchical approach. Next, SVM classifier was adopted to evaluate the capability of multispectral data (i.e. Operational Land Imager, OLI and SPOT 6) for determining the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*. The results showed that SPOT 6 had a higher overall accuracy of 83.33% than OLI, i.e.76.39%. While SPOT 6's the higher spatial resolution was useful for better characterisation of the distribution and patch sizes, the study found that the spectral configuration of OLI was more important in identifying possible locations infested by *P. hysterophorus*. Overall, the study demonstrated that fewer spectral bands selected by the proposed hierarchical approach have the greatest potential for reliably discriminating IAP species using airborne and satellite hyperspectral sensors. The study also demonstrated that the current information needs on IAP's can be addressed using accessible multispectral data, valuable for effective land management, site specific weed management, and site prioritisation.

DEDICATION

To my dear daughter, Oarona, you give me courage and strength to live each day.

To my dearly loved mother; Rebecca, my sisters; Lydia and Magdeline, my brothers; Joseph (late), William and Thapelo, my nephews and my fiancée and best friend, Milly Mohlono, for your motivations, laughter, love, and prayers that have kept me going.

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CHAPTER 1

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Invasive alien Plants (IAP's), also known as exotic weeds are non-indigenous plants introduced naturally, accidentally and/or deliberately by humans in a new geographical environments (Mandal, 2011). Modernity and globalisation have particularly played a major role in the spread of IAP's. In the recipient environment, the IAP's grow rapidly, often out-competing native species for nutrients, water and space (Dogra et al., 2010, He et al., 2011). Consequently, IAP's can among others alter ecosystem processes and functions, biodiversity, vegetation health and agricultural production in their new colonies.

Parthenium hysterophorus (known in variant names that include Carrot grass, Bitter weed, Star weed, White top, Wild feverfew, the “Scourge of India”, Congress grass or Famine weed) is one of the most widely spreading and problematic invasive weeds across the globe (Patel, 2011, McConnachie et al., 2011, Dhileepan and McFadyen, 2012). It is an erect, ephemeral and herbaceous weed thought to originate from Mexico, Central and South America. In the past century, its invasion has been reported in among others North America, the Caribbean, Southern and Eastern Africa, the Indian Ocean islands, Australia and India (Dhileepan, 2007, Patel, 2011). Under favourable climatic conditions (rainfall >500mm per annum and temperatures from 10 to 25°C) it grows rapidly, up to 1.8 m or higher and produces creamy-white flowers in four to six weeks after germination (Kumari and Kohli, 1987, Kandwal et al., 2009, Khan et al., 2012). Dhileepan (2007) and Adkins and Shabbir (2014) note that in ideal conditions, *P. hysterophorus* may germinate, grow and flower any time of the year. Each plant produces about 20 000 seeds that can persist for several years. Due to their light weight, they can be easily dispersed for longer distances by farm machinery, livestock, vehicles, wind, floods or flowing water and germinate rapidly in favourable conditions (Javaid et al., 2009, McConnachie et al., 2011, Dogra, 2011). The longevity and persistence of seeds in the soil during dry conditions, when native vegetation is commonly reduced necessitates longer movement of grazing animals in search for pasture, further increasing the seed distribution. This characteristic makes *P. hysterophorus* extremely difficult to control and eradicate.

A number of studies, among others (Dhileepan, 2007, McConnachie et al., 2011) have reported its severe impacts on ecosystem processes and functions, biodiversity, agriculture and human health. In Australia for instance, Dhileepan (2007) note that native grass species decline with

increasing *P. hysterophorus* biomass, resulting in reduced pasture production while Nigatu et al. (2010) found that dry grass biomass in Ethiopian pasture land was reduced by 28.9%, 59.4% and 90.4% in the low, medium and high *P. hysterophorus* infested areas respectively. Throughout its lifecycle, *P. hysterophorus* releases toxic chemicals which inhibit germination and growth of co-existing vegetation (McConnachie et al., 2011). In India for instance, Dogra et al. (2009) found that *P. hysterophorus* significantly reduce the natural habitats and decrease productivity and diversity of native plants, consequently altering the structure, function and dynamics of habitats. It has been reported that prolonged human exposure to *P. hysterophorus* causes hay fever, bronchitis, dermatitis, allergic rhinitis, black spots, diarrhoea, skin inflammation and asthma (McConnachie et al., 2011). In livestock, the weed causes a reduction in quality of milk and milk products and death, if significant amounts are consumed, (McConnachie et al., 2011, Strathie et al., 2011) while in wildlife, it may cause degenerative changes in liver and kidney (Patel, 2011).

In South Africa, *P. hysterophorus* has been identified as a major threat to grazing and croplands of northern KwaZulu-Natal province (Belz et al., 2007, Strathie et al., 2011). The weed has also been found in Mpumalanga, North West and Limpopo provinces (Belz, et al. 2007; Strathie, et al. 2011). Using a climatic suitability distribution model (CLIMEX), McConnachie et al. (2011) demonstrated that other provinces, particularly those bordering highly infested countries such as Swaziland and Mozambique are at high risk of invasion. Such findings necessitate accurate and up-to-date information on the locations and distribution of *P. hysterophorus* to design relevant mitigation measures. According to Franklin (2010) there is paucity of such information for environmental research, resource management and conservation planning. Additionally, information on spatial patterns of IAP's is important for establishing ecological links to underlying ecosystem diversity, structure and processes and habitats changes (Turner et al., 2003).

Traditionally, the information on spatial patterns of IAP's has relied heavily on the field-based surveys. However, such techniques are often labour intensive, time consuming and costly (Taylor et al., 2011). Cho et al. (2015) for instance note that IAP's invading large and remote areas are hardly surveyed because of point-based nature of the surveying methods. According to Dorigo et al. (2012) the patchy nature in most emerging IAP species make them particularly difficult to identify and locate in highly heterogeneous landscapes. For these reasons, availability of information on *P. hysterophorus* distribution in South Africa are limited to coarse scale, i.e. quarter degree (Henderson, 1999). Previously, aerial photography have been adopted (Everitt and Judd, 1989), however their spectral and temporal intervals and cost may not be perfectly

optimised to characterise IAP's distributions for operational purposes. For example, Lass et al. (2005) note that factors such as high cost of colour-infrared photographs, photo processing and interpretation, absence of quantitative data, variable interpretation and requirement for manual scanning or digitizing have limited their application for detecting IAP's. These challenges have opened up opportunities for adoption of remotely sensed data for IAP species mapping.

1.1.1. The potential of Remote Sensing for IAP species discrimination

Remote Sensing has the capability to provide detailed quantitative land surface information at various spatio-temporal scales at relatively lower cost. Its unique data characteristics and capability to combine various methods (such as statistical models and mathematical algorithms) provide powerful and objective ways of determining landscape composition. The use of data captured by remote sensing is an attractive option for early detection, discrimination and mapping of IAP's, valuable for generating optimal mitigation strategies. Remote sensing measurements capture electromagnetic energy from IAP's in various wavelengths, hence enable the detection and assessment of their bio-chemical and bio-physical properties (Jensen, 1983). The interaction of electromagnetic radiation with plant leaves, i.e. reflectance, absorption or transmittance, depends on plant's bio-physical properties such as leaf tissue density, arrangement, size, age, structure, texture and thickness. Furthermore, length of the plant stem, presence of flowers and fruits and bio-chemical characteristics such as proteins, lipids, starch, cellulose, chlorophyll, nitrogen, water and oil determine the spectral reflectance characteristics (Clark and Roush, 1984, Narumalani et al., 2009, Usha and Singh, 2013). For example, carotenoids, xanthophyll, anthocyanin and chlorophyll pigments are primarily absorbed in the blue (i.e. 450nm-520nm) and red (i.e. 630nm-600nm) regions of electromagnetic spectrum, while the spongy mesophyll cells result in high reflectance in the 700-1200nm range that constitute the near-infrared region (Jensen et al., 2007) (see Figure 1).

These spectral properties have been the basis for most vegetation studies, including the development of empirical techniques such as vegetation indices for estimating leaf area index (LAI) and biomass (Shen et al., 2009). Spectroscopy; the study of the interaction of electromagnetic energy and earth's surface features is commonly studied at field level and forms the basis of most air-borne and satellite-based imaging systems (Milton et al., 2009). Therefore an understanding of the spectral signatures of IAP species and their co-existing species allows for an assessment of the feasibility of identification and discrimination prior to mapping activities.

1.1.2. Hyperspectral remote sensing of IAP species

Hyperspectral data contains reflected electromagnetic energy from an area of interest in hundreds of contiguous narrow band intervals (see Figure 1) (Jensen et al., 2007). The added spectral resolving power allows for discrimination of subtle intra and inter-species reflectance differences (Narumalani et al., 2009). A distinct advantage of hyperspectral data is their inherent capability to provide high spectral information on, and capture minute differences in the biophysical and biochemical properties of vegetation (Xu et al., 2009, Usha and Singh, 2013). These properties allow species discrimination based on their absorption of specific regions of the electromagnetic spectrum (Jia et al., 2011, Chun et al., 2011). Figure 1 shows an example of a contiguous canopy hyperspectral signature of *P. hysterophorus* (PH) and band positions of Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI). Additionally, main factors affecting the spectral signature across 400nm-2500nm regions of the electromagnetic spectrum are shown (Adam et al., 2010, Adjorlolo et al., 2012b). The red-edge indicate a transition region of rapid change in reflectance between strongly absorbed red region and highly reflected NIR region and is renowned for its high sensitivity to small changes in canopy chlorophyll content, gap fraction and senescence (Potter et al., 2012).

Figure 1. Factors affecting reflectance properties in various regions of electromagnetic

spectrum and a comparison of contiguous spectral signature of *P. hysterophorus* (PH) and discrete band positions of multispectral data (Landsat 8 OLI).

Whereas airborne and spaceborne hyperspectral image data have been known to generate highly reliable IAP species classifications (Yang and Everitt, 2010, Yang et al., 2011, Olsson and Morisette, 2014), they are often costly and have limited global coverage, and therefore currently limited to a small number of projects (Narumalani et al., 2009, Huang et al., 2009, He et al., 2011). Furthermore, existing sensors e.g. EO-1 Hyperion and Compact High Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (CHRIS) are insufficient (Buckingham and Staenz, 2008); hence there are significant data gaps in most invaded areas. Alternatively, leaf and canopy level hyperspectral measurements using field spectrometers have been used to understand the reflectance properties of various species for discrimination purposes (Schmidt and Skidmore, 2003, Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Fernandes et al., 2013), to estimate biochemical properties such as nitrogen content (Bajwa et al., 2010, Wei et al., 2012), chlorophyll content (Xu et al., 2009) and leaf-water content (De Jong et al., 2014, Mirzaie et al., 2014). Canopy hyperspectral data are cheaper to acquire and allow for in-depth understanding of spectral signatures of IAP species in a heterogeneous landscape for mapping. For example, Fernandes et al. (2013) note that optimal spectral bands selected from canopy hyperspectral measurements are essential for selecting most suitable satellite imagery for mapping. However, the adoption of canopy hyperspectral data is often limited by their characteristic high data dimensionality, often resulting into lower classification accuracies and high computational requirements (Pal and Foody, 2010). A novel approach to select optimal spectral subset of bands that yield improved classification accuracy and optimises computation is therefore proposed in chapter 2 of this dissertation.

1.1.3. Multispectral remote sensing of IAP species

For decades, multispectral remotely sensed data has been adopted to monitor the spread and determine the distributions of IAP's. Multispectral sensors capture reflected and emitted energy from an area of interest in multiple broad band intervals (i.e. ~4 to 36) of the electromagnetic spectrum (see Figure 1) (Jensen et al., 2007). To date, a wealth of historical and current low or no cost multispectral data at different spatial and temporal resolutions exist (see Table 1). As a result, researchers have extensively applied remotely sensed data from multispectral sensors such as MODIS, NOAA/AVHRR, Landsat, ASTER and SPOT to monitor the spread and determine the spatial distributions of IAP'S (Huang and Asner, 2009, Viana and Aranha, 2010, Zong et al., 2010, Frazier and Wang, 2011, Qu et al., 2011). For example, moderate spatial resolution (30m) data from Landsat TM, with six spectral bands in visible (VIS), near-infrared (NIR) and

shortwave infrared (SWIR) and SPOT 5, with 4 spectral bands in VIS, NIR and SWIR and a 10m spatial resolution have allowed for the detection of *Spartina alterniflora* (saltmarsh cordgrass) with overall accuracies of 71% to 78.8% in China (Zong et al., 2010). Laba et al. (2008) obtained overall accuracies of between 64.9% and 73.6% when mapping *Trapa natans* (water chestnut), *Phragmites australis* (common reed), and *Lythrum salicaria* (purple loosestrife) using Quickbird data (4 spectral bands in the VIS and NIR at 2.4m spatial resolution). Generally, medium resolution sensors have been found useful for mapping larger patches, i.e. >0.5 ha (Arzandeh and Wang, 2003).

Recent studies (Lantz and Wang, 2013, Adelabu et al., 2013, Müllerová et al., 2013) have shown that very high spatial resolution data (i.e. <1m) combined with additional narrow bands, i.e. red edge and yellow have high capability of detecting and discriminating species. Using Worldview-2 imagery, with 8 multispectral bands and 2m spatial resolution for instance, Lantz and Wang (2013) mapped the distribution of *Phragmites australis* (common reed) in a coastal wetland, achieving a classification accuracy of 94%. Generally, developments in multispectral instruments are expected to enable higher classification accuracies and provide further opportunities for testing classification algorithms used for discriminating and determining IAP's distributions. Such new generation sensors include Worldview-3, which offers very high spatial resolutions (1.24m-multispectral, 31cm-panchromatic, 3.7m-SWIR 3.7m, and 30m-Clouds, Aerosols, Vapours, Ice, and Snow bands (CAVIS)) with super spectral resolution (8 VNIR bands; 8 SWIR bands and 12 CAVIS bands). However, whereas very high resolution data may provide higher classification accuracy, they are often costly for operational applications. Consequently, data accessibility and cost from heritage missions such as SPOT and Landsat provide an opportunity for mapping the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* in infested areas of Kwa Zulu Natal province. SPOT 6 (launched in 2012), in comparison to its predecessor, has an improved spatial resolution (i.e. 6m - multispectral bands, 1.5m - panchromatic band) and four spectral bands in Visible and NIR regions. On the other hand, Landsat 8 (launched in 2013) has 10 spectral bands in Visible, NIR, SWIR and TIR regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. These datasets were evaluated for mapping the distribution and patches of *P. hysterophorus* in Chapter 3 of this study. Table 1 outlines some of the potential data for mapping IAP species.

Table 1. Potential multispectral data for mapping IAP species.

Moderate Resolution Sensors (<30m)							
Sensor	PAN	Multispectral	Swath width	Revisiting Period	Archive	Programmable	Accessibility
Landsat 8 OLI	15m	30m (VNIR, CB, 2×SWIR	185km	16 days	2013	No	Free
ASTER		15m (V + 2×NIR), 30m (5×SWIR)			1999	Yes	US\$80/60km ²
High Resolution Sensors (<10m)							
SPOT 5	2.5m	10m (VNIR) & 20m (SWIR)	60km/120km	26 days	2002	Yes	Free for non-commercial use in SA
SPOT 6 & 7	1.5m	6m (VNIR)	60km	1 to 3 days	2013	Yes	Free for non-commercial use in SA, otherwise US\$5.15/km ²
Quickbird	0.6m	2.4 (VNIR+RE)	16.5km	1 to 3 days	2002	Yes	US\$16/km ²
RapidEye		6.5m (VNIR+RE)		1 day	2008	Yes	US\$1.28/km ²
IKONOS	0.82m	3.2m (VNIR)	11km	1 to 3	1999	Yes	US\$10/km ²
Very High Resolution Sensors (<0.5m)							
GeoEye-1	0.5m	2m (VNIR)	15.2km	1 to 3	2008	Yes	US\$16/km ²
Pleiades	0.5m	2m	20km	Daily	2012	Yes	US\$13/km ²
WorldView-2	0.5m	2m (V, CB, 2×NIR, RE, Y)	16.4km	Daily	2009	Yes	US\$16/km ²
WorldView-3	0.31m nadir/ 0.34 off- nadir	1.24m nadir/1.38m off-nadir (V, CB, 2×NIR, RE, Y); 3.70m nadir/4.10m off-nadir (8×SWIR) & 30m nadir (CAVIS)	13.1 km	<1 day	2014	Yes	US\$32/km ²
Acronyms : ‘V’=standard Blue, Green & Red bands; ‘CB’ =coastal/aerosol ‘NIR’=Near Infrared band; ‘Y’=Yellow band, ‘RE’=Red Edge, ‘SWIR’=Short-wave Infrared, ‘TIR’=Thermal Infrared band, ‘CAVIS’=Clouds, Aerosol, Vapours, Ice and Snow bands							

1.1.4. Classification algorithms and vegetation indices for discriminating IAP species

For decades, various parametric algorithms such as ISODATA, Parallelepiped, Minimum Distance to Means (MDM) and Maximum Likelihood Classifier (MLC) have been used on remotely sensed data. Such algorithms have *a priori* assumptions that the data is normally distributed and utilise image statistics (such as mean, standard deviation and covariance matrices) to allocate pixels to clusters (Memarian et al., 2013). Arzandeh and Wang (2003) achieved overall accuracies of between 82% and 87% using MLC and multispectral data from SPOT, Landsat and Indian Remote Sensing Satellite (IRS) for monitoring *Phragmites australis*

(Common reed). Whereas ISODATA and MLC have been the most commonly used parametric algorithms, for monitoring and determining IAP's spatial distribution (Theriault et al., 2006, Viana and Aranha, 2010, Everitt et al., 2005), other studies (Chi et al., 2008, Mountrakis et al., 2011) have established that classification using parametric algorithms is tedious (requiring enormous training samples), and yield poor classification results when highly dimensional data and small training sample are used. Furthermore, parametric algorithms do not take into account the complexity of class distributions in multi-temporal datasets, i.e. non-normality and multimodality (Gavier-Pizarro et al., 2012).

On the other hand, non-parametric machine learning algorithms such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM), Random Forests (RF), Decision Trees (DTs) and Support Vector Machines (SVMs) have no prior assumptions about the data, can incorporate ancillary data, and are flexible and adaptable (Carpenter et al., 1997). Such algorithms have recently been successfully adopted on both hyperspectral and multispectral data (Pal and Mather, 2004, Gavier-Pizarro et al., 2012, Adelabu et al., 2013, Yagoub et al., 2014, Atkinson et al., 2014). SVM was adopted in Chapter 2 and 3 of this dissertation for spectral discrimination and mapping the distribution and patches of, *P. hysterophorus*.

1.1.5. Challenges and opportunities for discrimination of *P. hysterophorus*

In hyperspectral remote sensing of vegetation, challenges such as multicollinearity and multidimensionality are commonly encountered (Adjorlolo et al., 2013, Peerbhay et al., 2013, Pal, 2006). The Hughes phenomenon, also known as the 'curse of dimensionality' reduces the performance of the classifier when there is limited training data (Hughes, 1968). In addition, narrow and contiguous spectral bands in hyperspectral data are often correlated with one another, resulting in highly unstable parameter estimates hence, increasing the generalization error of a classifier (Clevers et al., 2007, Mirzaie et al., 2014). Although several techniques have been proposed to overcome these challenges, none of them has been proven superior (Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Jia et al., 2011). This provides an opportunity to test the performance of other innovative techniques for dimensionality reduction and to improve classification accuracy.

In multispectral image classification, phenomena such as mixed pixels and spectral confusion are common, where the former refers to pixels that contain two or more classes and the latter occurs when two or more classes have similar reflectance properties (Hsieh et al., 2001, Yang et al., 2011). Medium resolution (i.e. 10 – 30m) images often have pixels that cover larger areas, hence patches of *P. hysterophorus* that cover smaller proportion of each pixel are likely to be

missed by the hard classifiers. For example, using Landsat TM to distinguish between native vegetation and an invasive species *Pennisetum ciliare* (buffelgrass), Olsson et al. (2011) found very low classification accuracy due to the heterogeneity of the landscape which resulted in mixed pixels.

Generally, studies have indicated that higher spatial resolution image data (i.e. <10m) offer greater resolving power, hence a higher probability that smaller patches can be detected with higher accuracy (Jensen, 1983, Dorigo et al., 2012). However, this is not always the case as spectral variability within one species, i.e. intra-species variability may be increased, resulting in spectral confusions and reduced classification accuracy. As noted by Hsieh et al. (2001), high spatial resolution imagery provides a wealth of spatial information about various objects on the ground; however the classification results are not always as promising as can be expected. In addition, it is challenging to distinguish IAP species from native species using discrete and broad wavelengths in multispectral images, since these are less capable of defining minute spectral differences between species. *P. hysterophorus* has sporadic growth and rapid spread; hence usually have varying patch sizes. This variability in patch sizes and different phenology of one species in an image may yield high uncertainty in the derived classification (Muad and Foody, 2012). As a result, a fair compromise between the spectral and spatial resolutions is fundamental when choosing data for mapping IAP's.

1.2. Research problem

Parthenium hysterophorus (Parthenium weed) has been identified as one of top 7 most devastating weeds in the world. Considerable impacts on ecosystem processes and functions, biodiversity, agriculture and human health have been reported. Hence, eradication and control of the species has recently become the focus in literature, with several interventions being proposed. In South Africa, *P. hysterophorus* invades savanna landscapes of northern KwaZulu-Natal where it has become dominant. As a result, it need to be eradicated and controlled to prevent further spread and introductions into new areas. Accurate and up-to-date information on the locations and distribution of *P. hysterophorus* is required for designing relevant mitigation measures. However, traditional field-based methods are costly, tedious, unsustainable and inappropriate for large and inaccessible areas. In that regard, remotely sensed data from hyperspectral and multispectral sensors can be exploited for providing useful information critical for effective weed management and site prioritisation.

This study sought to address the following research problems:

- i. The inherent high dimensionality in hyperspectral data reduces classification accuracy due to Hughes effect.
- ii. Among existing feature selection techniques, there is no single technique that has been proved superior in literature, hence an opportunity exist to explore other techniques.
- iii. The usefulness of the spatial and spectral configurations of OLI and SPOT 6 datasets for characterizing the patches of *P. hysterophorus*, have never, to the best of our knowledge, been explored.

1.3. Aim and Objectives

1.3.1. Aim

The aim of this study was to explore the capability of hyperspectral and multispectral data for discriminating and mapping *Parthenium hysterophorus*.

1.3.2. Objectives

The objectives of the study were:

- (i) To determine optimal subset of spectral bands from canopy hyperspectral data for accurately discriminating *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species.
- (ii) To evaluate capability of multispectral data from Landsat 8 OLI and SPOT 6 for determining *P. hysterophorus* distribution and patch sizes.

1.4. Research questions

This study attempted to address to the following research questions:

- i. What is the optimal subset of bands for discriminating *P. hysterophorus* from its co-existing species?
- ii. How can classification accuracy be improved by reduced subset of bands versus entire dataset?
- iii. What is the utility of the spectral and spatial configurations of multispectral data (i.e. OLI and SPOT 6) in mapping the patches of *P. hysterophorus*?

1.5. Scope of the study

This study explored the capability of hyperspectral and multispectral data for discriminating and mapping *P. hysterophorus* in the Savanna landscapes of northern Kwa Zulu-Natal province. A robust classification algorithm, i.e. Support Vector Machines (SVM) was used with canopy hyperspectral and multispectral datasets to discriminate *P. hysterophorus* from co-existing species and to determine its distribution and patch sizes, respectively. Specifically, Chapter 2 presents the potential of an innovative hierarchical approach to deal with high dimensionality in hyperspectral data and to improve classification accuracy of *P. hysterophorus* while Chapter 3 presents the capability of multispectral data for providing accurate information on *P. hysterophorus* distribution and patch sizes. According to (Turner et al., 2003), this information is fundamental in understanding the ecological links to the diversity, structure and processes of the ecosystem and habitats changes.

1.6. Study area

The study area is located in the northern part of Kwa Zulu-Natal province, South Africa (Latitudes 26°45' to 27°7' and Longitudes 22°7' to 32°20'; Figure 2). The area lies in the summer rainfall belt, with an annual range of 500 – 2000mm. Temperatures are cooler (13.9 °C) during winter and warm (21.7°C) in summer (Atkinson et al., 2014). The area falls within the savanna biome, characterised by open Lowveld savanna vegetation, shrubs and grasses. Common tree species include; Umbrella thorn (*Acacia tortillis*), Sweet thorn (*Acacia karroo*), and Tamboti (*Spirostachys Africana*) while grass species include Spreading prinklegrass (*Aristida congesta* subsp. *Barbicollis*) and Pinhole grass (*Bothriochloa insculpta*) that occur in highly disturbed areas and Redgrass (*Themeda triandra*) and Spear grass (*Heteropogon contortus*) that dominate less disturbed areas. The prevalence of non-native plants has become a serious problem in the area where IAP's such as *P. hysterophorus* have become increasingly prolific. *P. hysterophorus* infestations are particularly evident along roads, in croplands, along fences and backyards, disturbed grasslands and protected areas. *P. hysterophorus* was first recorded in Kwa Zulu Natal province in 1880 and again after the floods in 1984 caused by Cyclone Demoina (McConnachie et al., 2011). As a result, field surveys showed that Ndumo Game Reserve is one of the most heavily infested reserves in the province; hence communal rangelands surrounding the reserve are also infested. Spectroscopy data (Chapter 2) was collected within Ndumo Game Reserve (26° 54' 43" S and 32° 15' 48" E, total area 102 km²), while Landsat 8 OLI and SPOT 6 images (Chapter 3) covered the reserve, communal farmlands and settlements (26°45'00"S and 32° 00'00"E).

Figure 2. Study area

1.7. Chapter outline

CHAPTER 1: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

The chapter provides a general background to *Parthenium hysterophorus*, including its description, distribution and impacts, the advantages of using remote sensing data and algorithms for discriminating IAP species. An overview of common challenges in remote sensing of IAP's are also briefly discussed. Additionally, research objectives, description of the study area, and the scope of the study are outlined.

CHAPTER 2: DETERMINING THE OPTIMAL SPECTRAL SUBSET FOR DISCRIMINATING PARTHENIUM HYSTEROPHORUS

This chapter adopts field spectroscopy data for discriminating *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. A novel approach integrating statistical filters and Support Vector Machines – Recursive Feature Elimination (SVM-RFE) for dealing with multidimensionality and co-linearity is proposed. The performance (i.e. classification accuracy) of hierarchically selected bands was

compared to the performance of entire spectral data and a combination of 20 best spectral bands selected by SVM-RFE.

CHAPTER 3: EVALUATING THE CAPABILITY OF LANDSAT 8 OLI AND SPOT 6 FOR DISCRIMINATING INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES WITHIN THE SAVANNA LANDSCAPES OF KWAZULU-NATAL, SOUTH AFRICA.

This chapter explores the utility of multispectral data from Landsat 8 OLI and SPOT 6 sensors for discriminating *P. hysterophorus*. The goal was to determine the optimal data for providing useful information on the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* for control and eradication, environmental and resource management and conservation planning. A robust algorithm, Support Vector Machines was used for classifying both datasets. Each dataset was evaluated using confusion matrix.

CHAPTER 4: SYNTHESIS AND CONCLUSION

This chapter presents a synthesis of the main findings of study, discuss the relevance of the results, make necessary recommendations for future studies and provides the limitations of the study.

CHAPTER 2

DETERMINING THE OPTIMAL SPECTRAL SUBSET FOR DISCRIMINATING PARTHENIUM HYSTEROPHORUS

2.1. Introduction

Hyperspectral remotely sensed data have been proven to be valuable for discriminating woody vegetation, herbaceous plants and grass species in sub-tropical and savanna grasslands (Adjorlolo et al., 2013, Mansour et al., 2012, Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Jia et al., 2011, Peerbhay et al., 2013, Atkinson et al., 2014). The major advantage of hyperspectral data is their narrow spectral bandwidths and large number of contiguous spectral bands, which are useful for distinguishing subtle differences in vegetation features (He et al., 2011). The higher sensitivity of hyperspectral instruments to biophysical and biochemical reflectance properties of various vegetation types make such instruments useful for characterizing plants species (Bajwa et al., 2010, Jensen, 1983, Daughtry et al., 2000, Xu et al., 2009). However, for species discrimination, the utility of hyperspectral data has been commonly impeded by its inherent properties such as multidimensionality and multi-collinearity (Demir and Ertürk, 2008). Hughes (1968) observed that the addition of more dimensions lead to a decrease in classification accuracy when training sample is small, i.e. $n < p$. This phenomenon, also referred to as “the curse of dimensionality” or Hughes effect, causes highly unstable parameter estimates and hence high generalization errors for the classifier (Clevers et al., 2007). For example, Tadjudin and Landgrebe (1998) determined that parametric classifiers such as Maximum Likelihood (ML) are less capable of estimating mean and covariance statistics from multidimensional data, hence yield undesirable classification accuracies, particularly with limited training data.

More robust non-parametric classifiers such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) have been reported to efficiently handle noise and multidimensionality in hyperspectral data (Pal and Mather, 2004, Cortes and Vapnik, 1995). Studies (Pal and Mather, 2004, Pal, 2006) have adopted SVM classification algorithm using large training samples (>100 pixels per class) to overcome the Hughes effect. The major challenge is that acquisition of large training samples can be tedious, costly and time consuming, particularly where areas to be sampled are inaccessible (Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Jia et al., 2011). Using Airborne Visible InfraRed Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) and Digital Airborne Imaging Spectrometer (DAIS) datasets, Pal and Foody (2010) observed a significant decrease in SVM classification accuracy with an increase in dimensionality for small training data (≤ 25 pixels per class). The authors concluded

that the Hughes effect was more prevalent when a small training data was used. In this regard, feature selection and dimensionality reduction is fundamental to aid the classifier to use only the relevant subset of predictor features that capture relevant properties of the response variable (Camps-Valls and Bruzzone, 2005, Pal and Foody, 2010). Additionally, feature selection may reduce the computational costs related to processing hyperspectral data, thus reducing training time and simplifying classification tasks (Pal, 2009). Feature selection and dimensionality reduction prior to classification have consequently become necessary in hyperspectral data analysis and has led to better classification accuracies and increased computational efficiency (Zhang and Ma, 2009, Pal and Foody, 2010, Löw et al., 2013).

Feature extraction techniques such as principal component analysis (Mather, 2004), maximum noise fraction (Green et al., 1988) and partial least squares regression (Wold, 1995) transform the original feature-space in order to provide fewer de-correlated components sorted by their signal to noise ratio (SNR) (Huang et al., 2004). However, these techniques do not automatically select relevant spectral bands for the classification model (Chun and Keleş, 2010). Critically, these techniques use all spectral bands in the transformation, including redundant bands and may be insensitive to subtle differences that are helpful for the discrimination of species (Tsai et al., 2005, Yao and Tian, 2003). Filter-based techniques on the other hand evaluate the intrinsic worth of each feature based on some relevance index such as correlation coefficients, test statistics or information theory (Pal, 2009, Guyon and Elisseeff, 2006). Whereas they are computationally efficient, they do not use a classifier to evaluate the performance of each feature and often ignore the impact of class labels (Deng et al., 2013). Conversely, wrapper techniques such as Support Vector Machines - Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) (Guyon et al., 2002) use a classifier as a 'black-box' to evaluate the predictive worth of each feature while embedded techniques simultaneously perform feature selection and classification (Guyon and Elisseeff, 2006). However, the technique's high computational requirements has limited its wide adoption with commonly used classifiers (Pal, 2009).

Nevertheless, SVM-RFE (Guyon et al., 2002) are often preferred over filter-based and embedded models due to their high performance and ability to overcome orthogonality assumptions. This is achieved by adopting mutual information between features and using support vectors exclusively as a decision function (Pal and Foody, 2010). Typically, the technique uses the weight value calculated during the training stage of SVM as the ranking criterion for evaluating features (Zhang and Ma, 2009, Pal and Foody, 2010). Pal (2009) compared the performance of Greedy Feature Flip algorithm, Iterative Search Margin-based algorithm and SVM-RFE and

found that the performance of all the approaches were comparable when using best combination of 20 features selected by respective algorithms from both DAIS and AVIRIS datasets. Pal and Foody (2010) showed that smaller subsets of selected spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE, Random Forest and mutual information-based max-dependency (mRMR) techniques were equally significant to achieve comparable accuracies with the entire dataset. Other studies (Zhang and Ma, 2009, Li et al., 2011) found that SVM-RFE was affected by the dataset's noise and has high computational requirements. Generally, a number of studies, among others (Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Pal and Foody, 2010, Jia et al., 2011) have shown that different approaches result in dissimilar sets of optimal features due to different number and separability of classes, study objectives and nature of the dataset. This indicates that there is no single superior technique that can be used to select an optimal subset of spectral bands for improving classification accuracy (Yang et al., 2005). Therefore, this study presents the potential of a hierarchical approach for dimensionality reduction and subset size selection for improved classification accuracy.

The study implements an integration of both filter and wrapper approaches to effectively reduce dimensionality and concurrent selection of optimal subset of spectral bands for discrimination of IAP species in the study area. The first step of analysis involves Kruskal-Wallis analysis of variance (ANOVA) to identify spectral bands with significant differences in median at $p < 0.05$. In the second step, inter-band correlation and Area under Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (AUC-ROC) analysis are performed to remove redundancy while retaining relevant spectral bands using AUC as a goodness measure. In the final step, we apply SVM-RFE to select a minimum subset of spectral bands which together yield improved classification accuracy. Using spectral reflectance characteristics on an area characterized by *P. hysterophorus* IAP and co-existing species, we compare classification accuracy from the hierarchical approach against the accuracy achieved from entire spectral dataset ($n = 1633$) and a combination of 20 best spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE. The choice of IAP species discrimination, particularly *P. hysterophorus* in this study was based on several challenges in management of the species and mapping of its distribution using conventional methods.

2.2. Materials and methods

2.2.1. Species description

Parthenium hysterophorus (Parthenium weed) is regarded as one of the seven most aggressive and problematic weeds in the world (Dhileepan 2007). It is known to invade agricultural fields,

hence reduce agricultural production and affect livelihoods (Dhileepan, 2007, Patel, 2011). The weed is also known to invade ecological systems, reducing biodiversity and compromising ecological integrity and the ability to provide ecosystem goods and services (Dhileepan, 2007, Patel, 2011). Typically, *P. hysterophorus* rapidly invades and colonizes disturbed areas such as abandoned croplands, building peripheries, roadsides, fallow and overgrazed lands, waste lands and cultivated fields (McConnachie et al., 2011). Each plant grows sporadically and rapidly, flowers and produces approximately 25 000 light seeds, which are dispersible for longer distances by vehicles, water, animals, farm machinery and wind (Javaid et al., 2009, McConnachie et al., 2011, Dogra et al., 2011).

Throughout its lifecycle, *P. hysterophorus* releases toxic chemicals which inhibit germination and growth of co-existing species (McConnachie et al., 2011). This leads to a decline in pasture production (Dhileepan, 2007), dry grass biomass (Nigatu et al., 2010) and natural habitats and biodiversity (Patel, 2011). Prolonged exposure and excessive consumption has been reported to result in health complications in human populations, declined quality of milk and meat products from cattle and degenerative changes in liver and kidney of sheep and buffalo (Patel, 2011). Therefore, to mitigate these impacts, early detection is necessary for design and implementation of management and eradication measures. Hence a need to determine the most optimal bands for spectral discrimination of *P. hysterophorus*, valuable for mapping using remotely sensed imagery.

2.2.2. Data collection

2.2.2.1. Field sampling

Field survey of several *P. hysterophorus* infested sites was conducted to identify the distribution of *P. hysterophorus*. During the survey, it was also ensured that the conditions in which *P. hysterophorus* exists, including co-existing species were identified prior to spectral data collection. Based on the survey, 1×1m plots of homogeneous (>90%) juvenile *P. hysterophorus* canopy cover and co-existing species were delineated. A total of 149 plots with *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species were then randomly selected from the study area (see Table 2). This was done to account for intra-species variability and to ensure that both *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species were well represented. In each 1×1m plot, a minimum of three random positions were selected for hyperspectral measurements.

2.2.2.2. Hyperspectral data collection

Spectral reflectance characteristics were acquired using a Spectral Evolution PSR-3500 Spectrometer (Spectral Evolution, Inc. © 2014) with a 350nm–2500nm spectral range. The spectrometer has ~3.5nm spectral resolution at 350-1000nm, 10nm at 1500nm and 7nm at 2100. The spectral bands from 350-1000nm, at 1500nm and at 2100nm have nominal spectral sampling intervals of 1.5nm, 3.8nm and 2.5nm, respectively. The spectral measurement unit consisted of spectrometer, a handheld Personal Digital Assistant (PDA) device and a fiber optic cable attached to the pistol grip for easy handling. Garmin Montana 650 standard GPS with ±3m accuracy was used for locating and navigating to the sampled plots.

P. hysterophorus and co-existing species canopy reflectance measurements were taken from 1×1m plots in early December 2014 (see Table 2 and Appendix 1). The scale of measurement ensured that the spectral measurements were a representative mixture of radiance as determined by the proportion, physical arrangement and reflective and transitive properties of plants components (Clark and Roush, 1984). Each spectral curve was visualized on a PDA and noisy measurements (including those affected by shadows) replaced by new measurements before being recorded. Each observation measured by the spectrometer was an average of 10 scans, at optimized integration time with a dark current correction and plots were tagged with a GPS coordinate and a photograph. Each plot was represented by an average of 3-5 pure spectral measurements, taken from distinct random positions within a plot. A fiber optic cable with a 25° FOV was consistently held at nadir angle. Also, an observation distance of 0.5m above each homogeneous canopy was maintained in all measurements. This yielded a circular surface area measurement (i.e. instantaneous field of view - IFOV) with a radius of approximately 11.08cm. In each case, the IFOV was significant to measure the radiances from targets without the interference of background reflectance. To normalize target measurements and to minimize the influence of the change of atmospheric conditions and solar irradiance (Mirzaie et al., 2014, Darvishzadeh et al., 2008), a white reference panel (spectralon) reflectance was taken before and after each plot measurements. All reflectance measurements were taken on cloudless or near cloudless conditions between 10:00 and 14:00 South African Standard Time (GMT+02:00). This was necessary to limit the variability due to changes in sun angle (Bajwa et al., 2010); to avoid excessive shadows (Menges et al., 1985) and to minimize atmospheric perturbations and Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) effects (Darvishzadeh et al., 2008).

Table 2. The number of plots and measurements per species

Species	Number of Plots	Number of measurements
<i>P. hysterophorus</i> (PH)	65	195
Acacia trees (AT)	33	99
Grass species (GS)	19	57
Other plant species (OPS)	32	96

2.2.3. Pre-processing and analysis

2.2.3.1. Pre-processing

The original spectral measurements consisted of 1024 spectral data points, with varying spectral resolution and sampling interval. These were interpolated to 1nm using Cubic spline interpolation, yielding 2151 spectral data points. The interpolation to finer sampling intervals was necessary to minimize errors that may arise from varying spectral sampling interval and detector steps of the spectrometer (Clark and Roush, 1984, Gardner, 2003). The noisy spectral bands (350-399nm; 1350-1465, 1790nm-1960nm and 2350nm-2500nm) were removed from further analysis (Thenkabail et al., 2004). Noise removed spectral data were then subjected to Savitzky Golay Filtering (Savitzky and Golay, 1964) experimental procedures with linear and quadratic polynomials (i.e. $p = 1, 2, 3$) and different window sizes (i.e. $m = 5, 11, 25$). Savitzky Golay Filter with parameters $p = 2$ and $m = 11$, resulted in relatively smooth spectral curves, while closely maintaining the absorption features across all wavelengths (see Figure 3). Noise removal and Savitzky Golay (SG) filtering resulted in 1633 spectral data points for further analysis. Cubic spline interpolation and SG filtering were performed using “prospectr” package (Stevens and Ramirez–Lopez, 2014) in R Statistical software.

2.2.3.2. Data analysis

Due to the aforementioned challenge in determining the optimal spectral bands from high dimensional spectral data and lack of a single superior technique for selecting optimal spectral bands, we implemented an innovative hierarchical technique consisting of Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, inter-band τ correlation and AUC-ROC variable importance and SVM-RFE. Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA (Kruskal and Wallis, 1952) and post hoc Dunn’s test (Dunn, 1964) were used to test the null hypothesis that there is no significant differences between the median spectral signatures of *P. hysterophorus* and its co-existing species at 95% significance level ($p < 0.05$).

Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA is a rank-based non-parametric test used to compare multiple independent samples. Contrary to one-way ANOVA, it calculates a unique initial table with p-value of the test for all the wavelengths and all co-existing species simultaneously (Quinn and Keough, 2002). The difference between medians of spectral signatures was tested as opposed to difference of means since Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA does not assume a normal distribution of the data (Lehman, 1975). Additionally, Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA is robust on different sample sizes (Quinn and Keough, 2002).

Since the dimensionality of the data remained high even after significantly different spectral bands were identified by Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, we implemented inter-band correlation analysis using Kendall's tau (τ) and AUC-ROC variable importance. The correlation analysis was implemented to identify and remove redundant spectral bands with a correlation coefficient of >0.9 , while AUC-ROC variable importance was used to estimate the importance of each retained band (by correlation analysis) for discriminating *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. Kendall's τ (Joe, 1990) is a distribution-free measure of concordance between two observed variables. A pair of points (x_i, y_i) and (x_j, y_j) are said to be concordant if $(y_j - y_i)/(x_j - x_i) > 0$ and discordant if $(y_j - y_i)/(x_j - x_i) < 0$ (Joe, 1990). In the current study, a correlation coefficient of >0.9 was considered highly correlated for spectral bands of *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species being redundant. The spectral bands with correlation coefficient less than the threshold of 0.9 were subjected to AUC-ROC variable importance available in "caret" package (Kuhn, 2008) to determine their individual inter-species discriminatory ability. AUC-ROC variable importance for multiple classes uses one-against-all strategy to perform ROC curve analysis on each band with a series of cutoffs being applied to predict classes. For each cutoff, a two dimensional space is formulated, where sensitivity is the vertical axis and 1-specificity is the horizontal axis (see Formulae 1 and 2). Area under the ROC curve (AUC) is then calculated for each class using trapezoid rule and the maximum AUC across the relevant pair-wise AUC's is used as the variable importance measure. In essence, AUC is used as a goodness measure for judging whether each band is important or not, where an area of 1 represents absolute importance and an area of 0.5 indicates that the spectral band has no discriminative power (Deng et al., 2013). Inter-band τ correlation and AUC-ROC variable importance allow filtering of redundant and less important spectral bands, while maintaining those with high discriminating power before SVM-RFE is applied.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \text{TP}/(\text{TP} + \text{FN}) \quad [1]$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \text{TN}/(\text{TN} + \text{FP}) \quad [2]$$

Where; TP, FN, TN, FP denote true positive, false negative, true negative and false positive respectively.

As a final step, we applied a wrapper feature selection approach, viz. Support Vector Machines - Recursive Feature Elimination, to automatically choose the optimal subset of features that yield high classification accuracy. SVM-RFE is a robust wrapper feature selection technique that uses an objective decision function $(1/2)\|w\|^2$ of SVMs to select optimal nested subset of features ordered by their discriminatory ability (Guyon et al., 2002). It uses backward feature elimination strategy, where a full set of features are used as the starting point of feature selection and features that cause changes in the decision function are progressively eliminated. At each iteration, the ranking scores of features are computed from coefficients of the weight vector w and the features with least score w_i^2 are recursively eliminated (where w_i^2 represents the corresponding i^{th} component of w). Unlike other feature selection techniques, SVM-RFE uses mutual information between features and the decision function is based solely on support vectors, thus eliminating orthogonality assumptions (Guyon et al., 2002, Pal and Foody, 2010). A detailed discussion of SVM-RFE can be found in Guyon et al. (2002) and Pal (2006).

2.2.4. SVM classification and validation

The SVM classification algorithm was applied to verify that selected wavelengths by the previous analysis can reliably discriminate *P. hysterophorus* (PH) and co-existing species. This was done to determine the optimal hyperplane with maximum margin (Boser et al., 1992). The procedure ensures that the samples with class labels ± 1 are located on the either side of the hyperplane and the distance (or optimal margin) of the closest training vectors (support vectors) is maximized, thus reducing the generalization error of the overall classifier (Vapnik, 1999). A training sample N can be represented by (y_i, x_i) , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, where y_i represents class labels ± 1 and x_i is a feature vector with n components. The linear SVM classifier is represented by the function $f(x, \alpha) \rightarrow y$, where α is the parameter of the classifier (Mercier and Lennon, 2003). In a nonlinearly separable problem, a regularization parameter C and kernel parameter σ are introduced. C is used to control the trade-off between the maximization of the margin between the training data vectors, decision boundaries and margin errors of the training data. On the other hand, σ is used to control the width of the kernel (i.e. polynomial, radial basis function (RBF) or sigmoid kernel), allowing SVM to distinguish multi-modal classes in a high dimensional space (Foody and Mathur, 2004). Decomposition approaches such as one-against-one and one-against-all have been developed to deal with multiple-class classification problems, since the original SVMs were developed for two-class problems. One-against-one approach applies $(M(M -$

1))/2 classifiers on each pair of classes and the mostly computed class label is kept for each vector, while one-against-all approach iteratively applies M classifiers on each class against the rest. M is the number of classes (Hsu and Lin, 2002, Mercier and Lennon, 2003). We used one-against-all approach with an RBF kernel and a 10-fold cross validation (CV) within “kernlab” R package (Karatzoglou et al., 2005). The tuning parameters for the classification model were selected by evaluating candidate pairs of a constant σ directly estimated from the training data by “sigest” function within “kernlab” and “caret” packages (Kuhn, 2008), and nine values of possible C parameters, i.e. 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16 and 32. Additional classification experiments were performed on entire spectral dataset and a combination of 20 best spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE for comparison with the hierarchical approach. Classification accuracy was assessed using confusion matrix and 95% confidence intervals (Congalton, 1991, Foody, 2002).

2.3. Results

2.3.1. *Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA*

Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA was used to determine if there are any statistical differences in spectral signatures of PH and co-existing species at $p < 0.05$. The analysis rejected the null hypothesis that there are no significant differences between the spectral signatures of PH and co-existing species. A *post hoc* Dunn’s test was used to determine the pairwise significance of each spectral band. The results are shown in Figure 3 and Table 3. Figures 3a, b, and c indicate the pairwise significance between spectral signatures of PH and each of the co-existing species, i.e. Acacia Trees - AT, Grass species - GS and Other Plant Species - OPS respectively. The grey areas highlight the spectral bands with significant difference between the PH and each of the co-existing species. The number of significant spectral bands were partitioned into six broad spectral regions (blue: 350 – 449nm, green: 450 – 549nm, red: 550 – 649nm, red-edge: 650 – 749nm, near infrared: 750 – 1299nm and shortwave infrared: 1300 – 2500nm) as suggested by (see Table 3). Figure 3d indicates the frequency of significant spectral bands between all possible species pairs. The significant spectral bands at $p < 0.05$ with higher frequency of occurrence (i.e. maximum grey shading) have greater statistical separability for PH and all other co-existing species.

Figure 3. Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA and post hoc Dunn’s test results for *P. hysterophorus* (PH) and Acacia Trees (AT) (a); PH and Grass species (GS) (b) and PH and Other Plant Species (OPS) (c). The shaded areas highlight all spectral bands that are significant for discriminating PH and other species at $p < 0.05$. The frequency of occurrence of significant spectral bands (d), where PH can be discriminated from all other co-existing species.

Table 3. Number of significant wavelengths for each pair of classes separated by broad spectral regions suggested by Fernandes et al. (2013). T denotes total number of input spectral bands.

Species pairs	No. of significant Spectral bands at $p < 0.05$					
	Blue (45 T)	Green (100 T)	Red (100 T)	Red-edge (100 T)	NIR (550 T)	SWIR (738 T)
PH vs. AT	100%	85%	64%	95%	100%	56%
PH vs. GS	100%	78%	50%	93%	100%	48%
PH vs. OPS	49%	26%	21%	71%	67%	31%

Generally, the results indicate that PH can be discriminated from its co-existing species in most spectral bands located in the visible, NIR and SWIR regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. It is clear from the results that most wavelengths in the green, red-edge and NIR regions were

mostly significant for discrimination of PH from co-existing species. The spectral signatures for PH and OPS seem to be closely related, since only a few wavelengths were significant in all spectral regions, with the exception of the red-edge region, 71% ($n = 71$) (see Table 3). When all possible pairs of species were considered, the results indicated that most spectral bands in the red-edge and NIR regions provided relatively higher statistical separability, followed by the SWIR and blue, green and red regions (see Figure 3d). This shows that the red-edge and NIR regions of the electromagnetic spectrum have a greater potential to discriminate the species than other regions. Overall, statistical significance test using Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA and post hoc Dunn's test, reduced data dimensionality by 63.32%, i.e. $n = 1034$. A total of 599 spectral bands were carried over for further analysis.

2.3.2. Inter-band correlation and AUC-ROC variable importance

The spectral bands selected by Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA and post hoc Dunn's test, i.e. $n = 599$; were highly correlated (see Figure 4). We therefore implemented Kendall's τ inter-band correlation analysis to identify and remove spectral bands with a correlation coefficient of >0.9 . These were considered redundant and added no independent information to the discrimination of PH and co-existing species.

Figure 4. Kendall's τ correlation analysis

The spectral bands resulting from inter-band correlation analysis were assessed for their individual discriminative ability of the species using AUC-ROC variable importance. The results are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Selected spectral bands and their associated AUC-ROC importance.

	Spectral bands (nm)						Total
	Blue	Green	Red	Red-edge	NIR	SWIR	
Kendall's τ <0.9	427	537	562	658; 685;707	1115	1966; 1971; 1982; 1990; 2003; 2005; 2013	14
AUC-ROC variable importance	0.89	0.94	0.95	0.93;0.95;0.99	0.99	0.96; 0.96; 0.96; 0.96; 0.95; 0.95; 0.95	

As indicated in Table 4, inter-band correlation and AUC-ROC analysis identified distinct spectral bands with high individual discriminative ability for PH and co-existing species, $n = 14$. Several spectral bands, i.e. seven; were selected in the SWIR region, three in the red-edge region and one in the blue, green, red and NIR regions respectively. AUC-ROC variable importance for spectral bands in most regions was high, i.e. >0.9 , with the exception of the blue region. Inter-band correlation and AUC-ROC variable importance were essential to further reduce dimensionality and collinearity prior to wrapper-based feature selection and to identify potential spectral bands for discrimination of PH and other co-existing species.

2.3.3. SVM-RFE

SVM-RFE was used as a final step in our hierarchical approach, and to judge the value of our approach with the same dataset consisting of highly dimensional hyperspectral data, $n = 1633$. The goal was to select a subset of spectral bands which together improve classification accuracy from filtered spectral bands (by statistical analysis above) and entire spectral dataset. SVM-RFE generated nested subsets of spectral bands that yield maximum CV accuracy. Based on 10-fold CV analysis, SVM-RFE selected 10 out of 14 spectral bands with better CV accuracy of 83.12%, compared to other subset sizes that were evaluated: 5 (79.34%), and 14 (79.15%). The optimal subset from the hierarchical approach consisted of red-edge band, 707nm which had the highest rank, followed by NIR band, 1115nm, SWIR bands, 1971nm, 1982nm, 1990nm, and 1966nm, red-edge band, 685nm and two SWIR bands, 2003nm, 2013nm and 2005nm accordingly. On the other hand, SVM-RFE on the entire dataset ranked all spectral bands according to their relative discriminatory importance for classification of *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species (i.e.

acacia, grass and other plants) and yielded better overall 10-fold CV accuracy of 89.16%. Other evaluated subsets of spectral bands were 20 (63.19%), 50 (64.39%), 100 (62.82%), 500 (83.76%), 1000 (78.76%), and 1500 (87.2%) (Figure 5). We selected and tested a combination of 20 best spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE based on previous studies (Pal, 2009, Pal, 2006) and entire spectral dataset for classification and comparison with our hierarchical approach.

Figure 5. Spectral subset sizes evaluated by SVM-RFE on statistically filtered and entire spectral datasets.

2.3.4. SVM Classification and validation

SVM classifier was used to determine the classification accuracy using entire spectral dataset, a subset of spectral bands selected by our hierarchical approach and a combination of 20 best spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE. Each dataset was partitioned by stratified random sampling to yield a 70% ($n = 107$) training and 30% ($n = 42$) validation datasets. Results (in Table 5) indicate that our hierarchical approach yielded a superior overall classification accuracy of 83.33% (95% CI = 68.64%, 93.03%). On the other hand, classification results using the entire spectral dataset (in Table 6) and a combination of 20 best spectral bands from SVM-RFE (in Table 7) had inferior overall accuracies of 78.57% (95% CI=63.19%, 89.7%) and 76.19% (95% CI=57.96%, 86.14%) respectively.

Table 5. Confusion matrix for hierarchical approach

Prediction	Reference				Totals	UA (%)
	PH	AT	GS	OPS		
PH	17	0	1	1	19	100.0
AT	0	7	0	1	8	50.0
GS	0	1	4	0	5	75.0
OPS	2	1	0	7	10	100
Totals	19	9	5	9	42	
PA (%)	94.73	88.88	60.0	44.44		
OA (%)	83.33% (95% CI = 68.64%, 93.03%)					

Table 6. Confusion matrix for entire spectral dataset

Prediction	Reference				Totals	UA (%)
	PH	AT	GS	OPS		
PH	18	0	0	0	18	100.0
AT	1	8	2	5	16	50.0
GS	0	1	3	0	4	75.0
OPS	0	0	0	4	4	100
Totals	19	9	5	9	42	
PA (%)	94.73	88.88	60.0	44.44		
OA (%)	78.57% (95% CI=63.19%, 89.7%)					

Table 7. Confusion matrix for a combination of 20 spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE

Prediction	Reference				Totals	UA (%)
	PH	AT	GS	OPS		
PH	16	0	0	2	18	88.88
AT	0	9	2	2	13	69.23
GS	0	0	1	0	1	100.0
OPS	3	0	2	5	10	50.0
Totals	19	9	5	9	42	
PA (%)	84.21	100.0	20.0	55.55		
OA (%)	76.19% (95% CI=57.96%, 86.14%)					

2.4. Discussions

The major limitation in the application of hyperspectral remote sensing for discrimination of IAP's has been the inherent multidimensionality in the dataset, with most studies opting for multispectral data (Laba et al., 2008, Viana and Aranha, 2010, Lantz and Wang, 2013). Hence, studies on techniques for dimensionality reduction and redundancy removal have recently become dominant in recent remote sensing literature (Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Pal and Foody, 2010, Jia et al., 2011, Adjorlolo et al., 2013, Deng et al., 2013). A growing interest in the potential of hyperspectral data is particularly due to the increasing current and planned availability of open-license hyperspectral data for land cover mapping and monitoring, e.g. Hyperion and Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMap). Additionally, due to their adverse impacts on food security, human health and biodiversity and ecosystem services, IAP's such as *P. hysterophorus* have become a global concern. A number of studies (Khan et al., 2012, Reddy et al., 2009) have recommended eradication of *P. hysterophorus* in its early growth stage. Therefore, this Chapter aimed to identify a spectral subset of bands with high discriminatory ability and therefore potential for early detection and discrimination of juvenile *P. hysterophorus* using satellite or airborne hyperspectral imagery. To achieve this, we applied a novel approach that integrates Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, inter-band correlation and AUC-ROC analysis and SVM-RFE for selection of optimal spectral subset of bands from highly dimensional data, $n = 1633$. The approach was benchmarked against entire spectral dataset and a combination

of 20 best spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE. A classification accuracy was used as an evaluation measure.

Results in this study showed that using the proposed approach, statistical analysis and wrapper-based models can be used conjunctively to select a minimum but optimal subset of spectral bands for discrimination of *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. The first stage of the hierarchical approach used Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA and post hoc Dunn's test at $p < 0.05$ to identify spectral bands that are significantly different between all species-pairs (i.e. PH and AT; PH and GS, and PH and OPS). Although, results suggested that the spectral signatures of *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species are statistically different in many bands ($n = 599$), the frequency of statistically different spectral bands was higher in the NIR and red edge regions (see Figure 3 and Table 3). This finding is similar to previous studies (Schmidt and Skidmore, 2003, Jia et al., 2011) and reinforces the importance of these regions for species discrimination.

This study did not directly quantify the biochemical and biophysical properties of *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species, however, the observed significant differences in reflectance and absorption properties in various spectral regions show the effect of such properties. The significant differences in reflectance in the red edge region can be attributed to differences in chlorophyll concentration and leaf area index between juvenile *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. This assertion is evidenced by physiological properties of juvenile *P. hysterophorus*, that are characterized by a short stem (2 - 6cm), about four to nine large dark green leaves spread on or close to the ground and each plant has a diameter of 6 to 30cm (Khan et al., 2012, Kumari and Kohli, 1987). These physiological properties ensured that effect of background soils (that otherwise would have caused reduced red-edge reflectance) is minimized. Also, due to its competitive nature relative to co-existing species, the differences in total pigment concentration, chlorophyll-a and nitrogen content cause significant differences in reflectance in the blue, green and red regions respectively (Blackburn, 1998, Gamon et al., 1997, Faurtyot and Baret, 1997). Canopy structure and water content in *P. hysterophorus* canopies were responsible for significant differences in the NIR region (Schmidt and Skidmore, 2003). Other subtle biochemical compositions such as water content, cellulose, protein, starch, and sugars may have caused significant differences in the SWIR (Curran, 2001, Carter, 1994). Overall, the results of Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA indicate that *P. hysterophorus* can be discriminated against its co-existing species in many ($n = 599$) spectral bands. The differences in canopy and leaf structure of *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species are indicated by Figure 6 below.

Figure 6. Differences in canopy and leaf structures of *P. hysterophorus* (a), Acacia Trees (b), Grass Species (c) and Other Plant Species (d)

The retained spectral bands by Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA had high dimensionality and were highly correlated (see Figure 4). AUC-ROC variable importance was adopted to evaluate each un-correlated spectral band for its predictive worth before being considered for further analysis. All un-correlated spectral bands had an AUC-ROC variable importance of >0.8 , indicating their high discriminatory ability (see Table 4). The conjunctive use of inter-band correlation and AUC-ROC variable importance was useful for retaining distinct spectral bands with high individual discriminatory ability, thus overcoming the shortcomings of statistical filters that do not take class labels into consideration as noted by Pal (2009) and Deng et al. (2013). Most of these spectral bands were located in the SWIR ($n = 6$) and red edge region ($n = 3$). The statistical filters were computationally efficient and spectral bands selected can be evaluated with different classifiers or wrapper-based feature selection techniques. As a final step of the hierarchical approach, SVM-RFE was adopted to select the optimal subset of spectral bands from the statistically filtered spectral bands by previous analyses. As shown in Table 7, this consisted of 10 spectral bands located in the red-edge region (685nm and 707nm), NIR region (1115nm) and SWIR region (1971nm, 1982nm, 1990nm, 1966nm, 2003nm, 2013nm and 2005nm). For

management of IAP's, these results imply that the selected subset of spectral bands have potential to effectively map *P. hysterophorus* in its early growth stage using satellite and/or airborne hyperspectral sensors.

SVM classification was used to assess the performance of the hierarchical approach, against entire spectral dataset ($n = 1633$) and combination of 20 best spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE (see Table 8). The hierarchical approach yielded the highest overall classification accuracy of 83.33%, outperforming both entire spectral dataset (78.57%) and combination of 20 best spectral bands from SVM-RFE (76.19%). Although SVM classifier has been shown to be robust to Hughes effect in other studies (Pal and Mather, 2004, Melgani and Bruzzone, 2004), this was not the case in this study. The lower classification accuracy of the entire spectral dataset may be attributed to its sensitivity to dimensionality, a finding consistent with Pal and Foody (2010) and Zhang and Ma (2009). Furthermore, the higher training (cross-validation) accuracy of entire spectral dataset, and subsequent lower classification accuracy are signs of over-fitting and generalization errors due to high number of correlated spectral bands. The combination of 20 best spectral bands from SVM-RFE were all within red-edge region (650nm – 749nm) and NIR (750nm – 1299nm) and were highly correlated, showing that SVM-RFE was not able to remove redundancy in the data. As a result, classification accuracy was compromised. The second stage of the hierarchical approach removed highly correlated bands and determined their individual discriminatory importance. This discriminatory importance of spectral bands for discrimination of *P. hysterophorus* is essential for land managers since it provide valuable information relating to biophysical properties of the species and may assist in choosing an appropriate sensor for mapping (Kuo et al., 2014).

Previous studies (Zhang and Ma, 2009) observed that SVM-RFE performs better than Modified Recursive SVM (MR-SVM) when feature space is limited to 5 to 10 spectral bands. Similarly, Pal and Foody (2010) suggested that a small subset of spectral bands (i.e. <12) would achieve comparable accuracy with entire dataset when there is a small training data available (i.e. <25 pixels per class). The higher classification accuracy obtained by the hierarchical approach in this study can be attributed to fewer ($n = 14$) statistically identified spectral bands with high discriminatory ability before SVM-RFE was applied, which then selected 10 optimal spectral bands. Prior statistical analysis ensured that kernel computation was optimized, hence reduced computation time of SVM-RFE (Zhang and Ma, 2009). Overall, the results suggest that using statistical filters and SVM-RFE feature selection conjunctively, may be beneficial for optimizing

the performance of SVM-RFE, improving classification accuracy of IAP's and reducing computation costs (see Table 8).

Table 8. Comparison of performance between the hierarchical approach, SVM-RFE and entire spectral dataset.

Feature selection approach	Subset sizes and performance		Tuning parameters		Training time (s)
	Number of spectral bands	Accuracy %	C	σ	
Entire spectral dataset	1633	78.57	2	0.0008693828	282.45
SVM-RFE	20 (Top best)	76.19	8	0.3173481438	15.73
Hierarchical approach	10	83.33	4	0.3547367	13.40

Note: Training time was based on 64bit computer, with Intel Core *i7* processor, CPU @ 2.2 GHz and 16GB RAM.

2.5. Conclusions

The objective of this chapter was to identify an optimal spectral subset of bands which maintains discriminative properties of the entire spectral dataset and yield better classification accuracy. To achieve this, we applied a novel approach that integrates Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, inter-band correlation and AUC-ROC analysis and SVM-RFE for selection of optimal subset of spectral bands from highly dimensional data, $n = 1633$. Results suggest that using the hierarchical approach, statistical analysis and wrapper-based technique, i.e. SVM-RFE can be used conjunctively to select minimum but optimal subset of spectral bands for discrimination of juvenile *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. At each stage of analysis, the hierarchical approach identified useful spectral bands offering greatest capability for discriminating all species-pairs. Therefore, these spectral bands have potential to discriminate juvenile *P. hysterophorus* and its co-existing species using current and next generation satellite and airborne hyperspectral sensors, offering potential for early detection and effective control of *P. hysterophorus*. We therefore conclude that the use of statistical filters and SVM-RFE can effectively overcome the problems of multidimensionality, computation and to some extent collinearity when compared to using SVM-RFE on canopy hyperspectral data. In addition, improved SVM classification accuracy was realized when using spectral subset selected by the hierarchical approach, than entire spectral dataset and a combination of 20 best spectral bands ranked by SVM-RFE. Although, it was not the objective of this study, the lower classification accuracy observed when entire spectral data is classified provide evidence that SVM classifier

is sensitive to Hughes effect. Therefore, feature selection prior to classification when $n < p$ can greatly improve classification accuracy, even when robust classifiers are used. Results in this study are valuable for operational discrimination and mapping of *P. hysterophorus* in its early growth stage using airborne and satellite hyperspectral sensors, thus may aid effective control and eradication the species.

CHAPTER 3

EVALUATING THE CAPABILITY OF LANDSAT 8 OLI AND SPOT 6 FOR MAPPING INVASIVE ALIEN SPECIES IN THE SAVANNA LANDSCAPES OF KWAZULU-NATAL.

3.1. Introduction

Globally, invasive alien plants (IAP's) species pose major threats to ecosystems, biodiversity, agricultural production systems and socioeconomic development imperatives such as sustainable human livelihoods. In particular, *Parthenium hysterophorus* (Parthenium weed) is one of the seven most aggressive and problematic weeds in the world (Patel, 2011). The allelopathic nature of the species, has seen it rapidly colonising disturbed areas such as abandoned croplands, building peripheries, roadsides, railway-tracks, fallow agricultural areas and overgrazed lands, waste lands and cultivated fields (McConnachie et al., 2011). As such, it has caused decline in pasture production (Dhileepan, 2007), dry grass biomass (Nigatu et al., 2010), and natural habitats and biodiversity (Patel, 2011). Under favourable conditions, *P. hysterophorus* may germinate, grow and flower in most seasons of the year (Dhileepan, 2007). As a result, research into optimal control mechanisms has increased in effort to contain and eradicate the species (Dhileepan, 2007, Khan et al., 2012, Reddy et al., 2009).

Effective management of *P. hysterophorus* and conservation planning depends on accurate and up-to-date information relating to its distribution patterns and patch sizes. Spatial distribution and patch sizes information is critical for understanding spatial and structural variability of IAP's in the landscape (Turner, 2005). In addition, accurate information about the spatial distribution and patch sizes would be useful for management and control of *P. hysterophorus*, and may aid proper planning and allocation of resources, hence site specific weed management. Thus, such (spatial distribution and patch sizes) information about *P. hysterophorus* would be invaluable to a wide range of specialists and non-specialists including environmental researchers, conservation and resource managers, and policy makers. However, such information has been limited or non-existent in the past due to accessibility restrictions and cost of traditional methods (Franklin, 2010). These methods involve point-based field surveys and manual digitising from aerial photographs are often laborious, time consuming, and costly, and have become less ideal for characterising structural properties of IAP's. Consequently, landscape and patch metrics based on remote sensing data have become popular since they are easily interpretable and better depict the changes in environmental resources and habitats (Kent, 2009). Landscape and patch metrics

calculated from FRAGSTATS spatial analysis program (McGarigal et al., 2002) have recently been deemed useful for quantifying the structure of landscapes (Kupfer, 2012), hence can be used to characterize the distribution patterns and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*. Satellite remote sensing data overcomes the limitations of the traditional methods because of their capability to provide data at various spatial and spectral resolutions in frequent and consistent time intervals. Remotely sensed data thus provides comprehensive areal coverage, contain quantitative information about the functional and structural characteristics of vegetation and present opportunities for accurate and timeous mapping of *P. hysterophorus* (Underwood et al., 2003). However, the accuracy of mapping IAP's is a function of several factors including spatial heterogeneity across landscapes, habitat types and variability of patch sizes (Dieleman and Mortensen, 1999, Smith et al., 2002). In addition, the inherent characteristics of the data such as its spatial and spectral configurations are fundamental in reliably determining IAP's patches and distribution. These factors also affect the subsequent landscape and patch metrics calculated from the data.

As noted by He et al. (2011), the spatial resolution determines the smallest object that can be mapped and the accuracy thereof. Jensen (1983) and Dorigo (2012) note that the smaller the spatial resolution, the greater the resolving power of the data. This explains higher mapping accuracies obtained with very high resolution data (i.e. <1m) from IKONOS, Rapid Eye, Worldview-2 and QuickBird sensors (Adelabu et al., 2013, Lantz and Wang, 2013). However, according to Hsieh et al. (2001), this is not always the case since the higher spatial resolution may complicate the classification process by introducing intra-species spectral variability, causing reduction in mapping accuracy. In addition, such data are costly for operational applications over large areas and require additional processing capabilities (Jensen, 1983).

Alternatively, medium (20 - 30m) and high (5 - 10m) spatial resolution data from heritage missions such as Landsat and Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre (SPOT) have visible and near Infrared (NIR) bands that are useful for mapping vegetation species. Additionally, they are available at low or no cost for civil applications (Table 1). Data from Landsat has been applied extensively for land cover mapping (Bradley and Mustard, 2005, Wessels et al., 2004), vegetation monitoring (Yang et al., 2013, Yang et al., 2012), species modelling and mapping (Zong et al., 2010, Viana and Aranha, 2010), among others. Landsat has more than four decades of medium resolution data covering the globe, while SPOT has about 29 years of relatively high resolution data. Recently launched sensors from these missions; Landsat Operational Land Imager (2013); hereafter OLI, and SPOT 6 (2013) continue to capture data on phenological,

functional and structural characteristics of vegetation sustainably and cost efficiency. However, the usefulness of the spatial and spectral configurations (i.e. band positions and bandwidths) of these sensors for mapping the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* is to the best of our knowledge poorly understood.

Various methods have been developed in the past few decades to improve classification accuracy in IAP's mapping using multispectral data acquired by different sensors. These algorithms are designed to take advantage of all spectral information contained in multivariate data to distinguish different land cover classes. Traditional parametric algorithms such as Maximum Likelihood have been extensively used for extraction of land cover information since 1980s (Lillesand et al., 2014). However, such algorithms do not take into account the complexity of class distributions in multiple datasets, i.e. non-normality and multimodality and perform poorly with limited training data (Gavier-Pizarro et al., 2012, Cho et al., 2012). Since it is often difficult to acquire large training samples due to cost, time, and accessibility (Adam and Mutanga, 2009), non-parametric algorithms such as Artificial Neural Networks (Atkinson and Tatnall, 1997, Carpenter et al., 1997), Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM), Random Forests (Breiman, 2001), and Support Vector Machines (Vapnik, 1999, Hsu et al., 2003, Burges, 1998) have recently become attractive for mapping vegetation at species level (Yang et al., 2011, Adelabu et al., 2013, Adjorlolo et al., 2012a).

The aim of this chapter was to determine the capability of multispectral data for providing useful information pertaining to the distribution and patch sizes of IAP species, *Parthenium hysterophorus*. Specific objectives were to evaluate the capabilities (spatial and spectral configurations) of OLI and SPOT 6 data for mapping *P. hysterophorus* and to compare landscape and patch metrics from these datasets, valuable for effective land management, conservation planning and site specific weed management. Support vector machines (SVMs) was used for classifying both datasets, because of its capability to handle complex, multi-collinear, and non-linear class distributions, and works better with limited training samples as compared to traditional parametric algorithms (Foody and Mathur 2004; Yang et al. 2011; Adelabu et al. 2013).

3.2. Data and materials

3.2.1. Data description

3.2.1.1. Remotely sensed data

The Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager OLI multispectral scene of path 167 and row 79 was acquired on February 12, 2014 at Processing Level 1T, i.e. Terrain Corrected and geo-rectified to World Geodetic System (WGS) 84 datum and Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) zone 36N coordinate system prior delivery. The image had minimal cloud cover (2.65%) and a root mean square (RMS) error of 4.701 pixels. In addition, an ortho-rectified SPOT 6 multispectral scene was acquired on April 28, 2013 and was delivered in WGS84/UTM zone 36S coordinate system. Both images differed in spatial, spectral and radiometric configurations as indicated in Table 9.

Table 9. Landsat 8 OLI and SPOT 6 characteristics.

Sensor	Spatial Resolution	Spectral regions	Spectral width (FWHM)	Swath width	Quantization
Landsat 8 OLI	30m	Coastal/aerosol blue (430nm - 450nm)	15.98nm	185km	16 bits
		Blue (450nm - 510nm)	60.04 nm		
		Green (530nm - 590nm)	57.33 nm		
		Red (640nm - 670nm)	37.47 nm		
		NIR* (850nm - 880nm)	28.25 nm		
		SWIR1* (1570nm - 1650nm)	84.72 nm		
		SWIR2* (2110nm - 2290nm)	186.66 nm		
SPOT 6	6m	Blue (450 nm - 520 nm)	166.0 nm	60km	12 bits
		Green (530nm - 590nm)	60.6 nm		
		Red (620nm - 690nm)	70.0 nm		
		NIR* (760nm - 890nm)	121.1 nm		

3.2.1.2. Training and validation data

Training and validation data were obtained from the field using a standard handheld GPS with $\pm 3m$ accuracy (see Appendix 2), and true colour aerial imagery with a 0.5m spatial resolution. GPS points were collected from *P. hysterophorus* patches greater than 5m. The data were partitioned into 70% training and 30% validation following stratified random sampling (Table 10).

Table 10. Training and validation datasets for classifying *P. hysterophorus*.

Classes	Class code	No. of training samples	No. of testing samples
<i>P. hysterophorus</i>	PH	85	36
Other Land cover	OLC	87	36
Total		172	72

Note: OLC included bare land, built-up, grassland, dense vegetation, shrub-lands, wetlands and water areas.

3.3. Methods

3.3.1. Pre-processing

Landsat 8 OLI image was re-projected to WGS84/UTM zone 36S, to match the SPOT 6 image. In addition, Landsat 8 OLI bands were stacked in the following order: coastal/aerosol blue, blue, green, red, near-infrared (NIR), shortwave infrared 1 (SWIR1) and shortwave infrared 2 (SWIR2). Atmospheric correction was performed on the both Landsat 8 OLI and SPOT 6 datasets using Fast Line-of-Sight Atmospheric Analysis for Spectral Hypercubes (FLAASH) module in ENVI (Cooley et al., 2002).

3.3.2. Support Vector Machines (SVM) Classification

Support Vector Machine (Burges, 1998, Hsu et al., 2003, Vapnik, 1999) is a state-of-the-art algorithm for data classification and regression. Several studies have compared the capabilities of SVMs with other algorithms for land cover classification (Foody and Mathur, 2004); species mapping (Adelabu et al., 2013) and invasive species distribution modelling and mapping (Pouteau et al., 2011, Gavier-Pizarro et al., 2012) with both multispectral and hyperspectral data. In its original form, SVM delineates two binary classes by fitting an optimal separating hyperplane to the training data in a multidimensional feature space (Janz, 2007). In this way, training samples with labels +1 and -1 are located on either side of the hyperplane and the margin between the closest training sample or support vectors and the hyperplane is maximised.

A search for optimal hyperplane with maximum margin ensures that the generalization error of the overall classifier is minimised (Vapnik, 1999). In a multi-class problem, decomposition techniques such as one-against-one and one-against-all have been developed (Hsu and Lin, 2002). In addition, a kernel function is used to project the input data into a higher dimensional space where the classes are not linearly separable. Linear, polynomial, radial basis function (RBF) and sigmoid kernels have been applied in literature, with RBF being common (Foody and Mathur, 2004, Krahwinkler et al., 2011, Kuo et al., 2014). A comprehensive mathematical description of SVMs is given in Burges (1998) and various SVMs variants as applied remote

sensing are reviewed in (Mountrakis et al., 2011). In this study, parameterisation was performed from “Kernlab” and “caret” packages (Karatzoglou et al., 2004) in R statistical software and classification performed in ENVI (Exelis Visual Information Solutions, Boulder, Colorado).

3.3.2.1. Parameterisation of SVM Classifier

The pixel values of known locations of *P. hysterophorus* extracted from the OLI and SPOT 6 datasets respectively, were used to find optimal parameters for SVM classification. The proper selection of these parameters is necessary, since they both significantly affect the classification results (Kaya, 2013). A Gaussian Radial Basis Function $K(x_i, x_j) = \exp(-\sigma \|x_i - x_j\|^2)$, $\sigma > 0$, x_i and x_j are feature vectors (Hsu et al., 2003) which requires the user to specify a regularization parameter (C) and a kernel parameter (σ), was adopted. The role of C parameter is to control the trade-off between the maximization of the margin between the training data vectors and decision boundaries and margin errors of the training data. This parameter allows SVM to deal effectively with potential noise in the data and class-confusions (Van der Linden et al., 2010). A σ parameter, on the other hand; controls the width of the kernel, allowing SVM to distinguish multi-modal classes in a high dimensional space (Van der Linden et al., 2010, Foody and Mathur, 2004). A Gaussian RBF kernel is regarded a universal kernel; therefore SVM model with Gaussian RBF can separate complex class distributions. The effectiveness of Gaussian RBF kernel has been reported in literature, with high accuracies and average processing times (Foody and Mathur, 2004, Krahwinkler et al., 2011, Kuo et al., 2014). The optimal tuning parameters were selected by evaluating a grid of candidate tuning parameters ranging from 0.01 and 1000 with a 10 fold cross-validation (CV). The optimal parameters were selected based on highest CV performance of different pairs of C and σ (Rabe et al., 2010, Atkinson et al., 2014).

3.3.3. Distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*

The patch sizes of IAP's are required on a yearly basis in order to aid effective site-specific weed management and appropriate allocation of resources (Heijting et al., 2007). This study defines two patch size classes, i.e. small (0.36 – 0.5 ha) and large (>0.51 ha), detectable with both OLI and SPOT 6 in order to make the maps comparable without bias towards higher resolution data. We used Mann-Whitney U test to determine the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between patch sizes calculated from OLI and SPOT 6.

The calculations of distribution and patch sizes were performed in FRAGSTATS 4.0 (McGarigal et al., 2002). FRAGSTATS is a spatial pattern analysis program for quantifying the structure

(i.e. composition and configuration) of landscapes. Landscape metrics such as Total class area (CA), Class percent of landscape (PLand) and Patch density (PD) were used in this study to characterise the distribution of *P. hysterophorus*. CA is a measure of the extent of the landscape that is comprised of *P. hysterophorus*, i.e. landscape composition. PLand measures the proportion of total area occupied by *P. hysterophorus*; while PD measures the number of *P. hysterophorus* patches per 100 ha. Furthermore, metrics such as Largest Patch Index (LPI), Number of patches (NumPatches) and Patch area (PArea) were used to characterise patch sizes. LPI measures proportion of total area occupied by the largest patch of *P. hysterophorus*, NumPatches measures the number of *P. hysterophorus* and PArea is the area of every patch classified as *P. hysterophorus* (Luck and Wu, 2002). Detailed descriptions and equations of these metrics are provided in (McGarigal et al., 2002).

3.3.4. Accuracy assessment and map comparisons

In most image classification, an accuracy assessment using a confusion matrix and kappa statistics is often expected (Congalton, 1991, Foody, 2002). However, Pontius Jr and Millones (2011) argue that Kappa is redundant and misleading for practical applications and propose that Kappa and its variants should not be used for accuracy assessment in remote sensing studies. Instead, Pontius Jr and Millones (2011) recommend two mutually exclusive measures, viz. quantity difference and allocation difference, which can be easily computed with a Pontius Matrix available online at <http://www.clarku.edu/~rpontius>. According to Pontius Jr and Millones (2011), quantity difference refers to the amount of disagreement between the two maps (i.e. reference and comparison maps) that result from imperfect match in the proportions of the classes. Allocation difference on the other hand refers to the amount of disagreement between the two maps (i.e. reference and comparison maps) that result from imperfect match in the allocation of the classes given their quantities (Pontius Jr and Millones, 2011, Pontius Jr and Santacruz, 2014). Pontius Jr and Millones (2011) and Pontius Jr and Santacruz (2014) point out that the allocation difference proposed is vague since it may be caused by both pairwise class confusions and non-pairwise confusions. Consequently, they partitioned allocation difference into two other components, i.e. shift and exchange differences that are caused by non-pairwise confusions and pairwise confusions, respectively. For the reasons provided in Pontius Jr and Millones (2011), this study adopted exchange (Formulae 3 & 5) and quantity differences (Formulae 4 & 6) for error assessment of SVM classification results from OLI and SPOT 6 because for shift to occur, at least 3 classes are required (Pontius Jr and Santacruz, 2014). In

addition, a confusion matrix was used to determine producer's (PA), user's (UA) and overall accuracies (OA).

$$e_j = \sum_{i=1}^J (\varepsilon_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ji}) = \frac{2 \times \{[\sum_{i=1}^J \text{MINIMUM}(c_{ij}, c_{ji})]\}}{\sum_{i=1}^J \sum_{j=1}^J c_{ij}} \quad [3]$$

Where; e_j is the exchange difference for class j , which is the sum of all exchanges that involve class j , i.e. all the exchange from i to J in some pixels and a transition from j to i in other identical number of pixels. c_{ij} is the number of pixels that are classified as i in a comparison map and j in reference.

$$q_j = \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^J (c_{ij} - c_{ji})| \times 100\%}{\sum_{i=1}^J \sum_{j=1}^J c_{ij}} \quad [4]$$

Where; q is the quantity difference for class j , in which $\sum_{i=1}^J (c_{ij} - c_{ji})$ is the sum of the difference between column total and row total for class j .

$$E = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^J e_j}{2} \quad [5]$$

Where; E is the overall exchange difference and is divided by two since summation of the numerator double-counts the class-wise exchange difference.

$$Q = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^J q_j}{2} \quad [6]$$

Where; Q is the overall quantity difference, computed from the sum of class-wise quantity difference and divided by two since this process double-count the class-wise quantity difference.

3.4. Results

3.4.1. Parameterisation of SVM classifier

The goal of parameterization was to identify the optimal regularisation C and kernel σ parameters, by systematically testing wide ranges of combinations using a 2-dimensional grid search with 10-fold cross validation accuracy (Janz, 2007, Rabe et al., 2010, Gavier-Pizarro et al., 2012). The optimal pairs of regularisation C and kernel σ parameters for both OLI and SPOT 6 datasets; i.e. 100 and 0.1 respectively were selected by grid-search.

3.4.2. SVM classification results

Support vector Machine (SVM) classifier was used for mapping *P. hysterophorus* infestations. The results of the classification from OLI and SPOT 6 were overlaid on SPOT 6 image, with

other land cover represented by the background (Figure 7). A visual assessment of the maps in Figure 7 below showed that *P. hysterophorus* infestations estimated from SPOT 6 were lower than in OLI.

Figure 7. *P. hysterophorus* infestations derived from Landsat 8 OLI (a) and SPOT 6 (b).

3.4.3. Accuracy assessment and map comparisons

The results of accuracy assessment using a confusion matrix (in Table 11) indicate that OLI had lower overall classification accuracy of 76.39% when compared to SPOT 6, 83.33%. OLI results for *P. hysterophorus* (PH) class had lower producer's accuracy (PA) of 55.56% and higher user's accuracy (UA) of 95.24%. On the other hand, SPOT 6 had higher PA, 72.22% and UA, 92.86% for the same class. By comparison, the PA for PH class was lower in OLI than in SPOT 6, while the UA was slightly higher in OLI and lower in SPOT 6, i.e. 2.38% difference. Table 3 shows confusion matrices of SVM classifications derived from OLI and SPOT 6.

Table 11. Confusion matrices for OLI and SPOT 6 datasets.

	Landsat 8		Totals	UA (%)	SPOT 6		Totals	UA (%)
	OLI				PH	OLC		
	PH	OLC						
PH	20	1	21	95.24	26	2	28	92.86
OLC	16	35	51	68.63	10	34	44	77.27
Totals	36	36	72		36	36	72	
PA (%)	55.56	97.22			72.22	94.44		
OA (%)	76.39				83.33			

Note: OA, PA and UA denote Overall accuracy, Producer’s accuracy and User’s accuracy respectively.

In addition to accuracy assessment by confusion matrix, two mutually exclusive components, i.e. quantity difference and exchange (allocation) difference as recommended by Pontius Jr et al. (2011) and Pontius Jr et al. (2014) were considered over kappa coefficient (Figure 8). *P. hysterophorus* classification from OLI had 10% quantity difference and 9% exchange difference. On the other hand, *P. hysterophorus* classification map from SPOT 6 had quantity and exchange differences of 13% and 5% respectively. In comparison, quantity difference in OLI was lower than in SPOT 6, whilst exchange differences were higher in OLI and lower in SPOT 6.

Figure 8. Overall Quantity and Exchange difference for Landsat 8 (Left) and SPOT 6 (Right).

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve variable importance (Kuhn, 2012) was computed to assess the relative contribution of each band to the classification accuracies of OLI and SPOT 6. The results (in Figure 9) indicate that band 5 (NIR band, 850nm - 880nm), band 3 (green band, 530nm - 590nm) and band 2 (blue, 450nm - 510nm) of OLI had greatest importance of 0.69, 0.68 and 0.62 respectively. Other bands 1, 6, 4 and 7 had ROC importance of 0.59, 0.58,

0.57 and 0.55 respectively. On the other hand, the NIR (band 4, 760nm - 890nm), blue (band 1, 450nm - 520nm) and red (band 3, 620nm - 690nm) bands of SPOT 6 showed the greatest importance, i.e. 0.56, 0.54 and 0.54 respectively mapping *P. hysterophorus*. The red band (band 3, 620nm - 690nm) had the lowest importance of 0.53.

Figure 9. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve variable importance for OLI and SPOT 6.

SVM classifications from OLI and SPOT 6 were compared using a contingency table (Table 12). The results indicate that both datasets correctly classified 70.83% of validation data, whilst only 5.55% was correctly classified in OLI but misclassified in SPOT 6 and 12.5% was misclassified in OLI but not in SPOT 6.

Table 12. Comparison of OLI and SPOT 6 data for mapping *P. hysterophorus*.

		Landsat 8		Σ
		Correct	Incorrect	
SPOT 6	Correct	51 (70.83%)	9 (12.5%)	60 (83.33%)
	Incorrectly	4 (5.55%)	8 (11.11%)	12 (16.67%)
Σ		55 (76.39%)	17 (23.61%)	72

3.4.4. Distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*

P. hysterophorus maps from OLI and SPOT 6 were used to calculate the landscape and patch metrics using FRAGSTATS 4.0 program. The results calculated from OLI indicate that 16.22% (i.e. 26619.12 ha) of the total study area (i.e. 164096.46 ha) was invaded by *P. hysterophorus*;

the LPI was 0.26%, NumPatches was 29 607 and patch density was 18.04 patches per 100 ha. On the other hand, the metrics calculated from SPOT 6 indicate that 6.38% (i.e. 10440.30 ha) of the total study area (i.e. 163629.89 ha) was invaded by *P. hysterothorus*; the LPI was 0.15%, NumPatches was 37 959 and patch density was 23.19 patches per 100ha. In comparison, the metrics calculated from OLI were markedly higher than those from SPOT 6, with exception of patch density. The results of the patch sizes calculated from OLI and SPOT 6 are presented in Figures 10.

Figure 10. *P. hysterothorus* patch sizes calculated from OLI and SPOT 6.

3.5. Discussions

3.5.1. The capability of multispectral data for mapping *P. hysterothorus*

Heritage missions such as Landsat and SPOT have a long record of remotely sensed data covering the globe. This study exploited the capabilities of the new data from these missions for mapping *P. hysterothorus* in an African savanna landscape. Despite their significant differences in spatial resolutions, the two have visible and infrared bands which are valuable for mapping vegetation species. Hence, have potential to characterize *P. hysterothorus* infestations in the study area. The results indicated that SPOT 6 had better performance, 83.33% overall accuracy than OLI, 76.39% (Table 13).

Table 13. Summary of SVM classification results from OLI and SPOT 6.

Dataset	Performance of OLI and SPOT 6 bands		SVM tuning parameters		
	Number of bands	OA (%)	C	σ	Number of SVs
Landsat 8 OLI	7	76.39	100	0.1	48
SPOT 6	4	83.33	100	0.1	68
McNemar's (X^2) test	1.92				

OA= Overall accuracy; OD=Overall Disagreement, SVs=Support Vectors.

OLI and SPOT 6 data showed different discriminatory abilities. The lower producer's accuracy in the PH class, i.e. 55.56% for OLI, than in SPOT 6, i.e. 72.22%, indicate higher thematic errors and uncertainty in OLI than SPOT 6. The reflectance of smaller patches of *P. hysterophorus* (than the pixel size of OLI) were likely overwhelmed by background reflectance from soils, co-existing vegetation and other land cover, hence were omitted from PH class. The sporadic growth and easily dispersible seeds characteristic of *P. hysterophorus* (Javaid et al., 2009, Dogra et al., 2011), and the availability of among others open disturbed land due to development of settlements, croplands and roads result in isolated and insignificant patches which caused spectral mixing within OLI bands. The thematic errors of omission (i.e. 1 - PA) in SPOT 6 were likely due to intra-species spectral variability (Hsieh et al., 2001) as a result of differences in *P. hysterophorus* growth stages. Such differences arise from species phenological characteristics that it can germinate, grow and flower any time of the year (Dhileepan, 2007), thus resulting in inconsistent spectral signature of *P. hysterophorus* within SPOT 6 image.

User's accuracy was slightly higher, i.e. 95.24% in OLI than in SPOT 6, i.e. 92.86%, thus implying reliability of both datasets and lower thematic errors of commission (i.e. 100 - UA). OLI's spectral capability to sample regions from 430nm to 2290nm provided additional information for separating *P. hysterophorus* from other land covers. ROC curve variable importance (in Figure 9) indicate that additional OLI's SWIR bands, i.e. band 6 (SWIR 1, 1570nm - 1650nm) and 7 (SWIR 2, 2110nm - 2290nm) had greater than 0.55 ROC importance in discriminating *P. hysterophorus* and other land covers. As noted by (Adjorlolo et al., 2012a), the usefulness of SWIR for discriminating species is not apparent, however it is often selected for discriminating species. In classifying shrubs, meadow and low density vegetation from Landsat TM and SPOT, Basham May et al. (1997) found that the presence of SWIR band in TM resulted in greater accuracy. In addition, Adjorlolo et al. (2012a) observed that the SWIR bands around 1540nm, 2280nm, and 2300nm were important for discriminating grass species. The greatest importance observed in bands 5 (NIR band, 850nm - 880nm), 3 (Green band, 530nm - 590nm) and 2 (blue band, 450nm - 510nm) can be attributed to their sensitivity to leaf and canopy biochemical and biophysical characteristics. Canopy structure and water content affect spectral

properties in the NIR region of the electromagnetic spectrum (Schmidt and Skidmore, 2003). On the other hand, the reflectance properties in the visible region are mainly due to pigment concentration, chlorophyll and nitrogen content (Blackburn, 1998). OLI's relatively narrow bands (bandwidth less than 60nm in the visible and NIR) as compared to SPOT 6 bands (see Table 9) also contributed to its better discriminatory ability and relatively lower commission errors (i.e. 1 – UA). Overall the findings in this study are consistent with (Taylor et al., 2011) who note that Landsat's comprehensive sampling of the electromagnetic spectrum, spectral resolution and band positioning were more important in mapping IAP's.

Similarly, red (band 3, 620nm - 690nm) and NIR (band 4, 760nm - 890nm) bands of SPOT 6 show the greatest separability with maximum ROC importance, i.e. 0.56 and 0.53 respectively in mapping *P. hysterophorus* (see Figure 5). Previous studies (Adelabu et al., 2013) observed that red and NIR bands from Rapid-Eye data were more important than red-edge band for mapping *Colophospermum mopane* and its coexisting species in a semi-arid environment. The blue (band 1, 450 nm - 520 nm) band showed similar importance as the red band. Slightly higher commission errors in SPOT 6 than OLI, were likely due its relatively broad bandwidths (all greater than 60nm) which resulted into spectral overlaps between *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. According to Taylor et al. (2011) these spectral similarities may have negative impact on mapping accuracy. Although it was not within the scope of this study to compare the effectiveness of classification algorithms, SVM algorithm adopted in this study showed effectiveness in discriminating such spectral overlaps between *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. This is evident from the observed higher number of support vectors (68) with SPOT 6 model as opposed to 48 in OLI model (see Table 13) which occurs when the classes are not separable (Rabe et al., 2010). Results in this study are thus consistent with previous studies that found that SVM was effective in handling complex, and non-linear class distributions (Yang et al., 2011, Foody and Mathur, 2004). Augmented by SVM algorithm, the broader and limited (only four) spectral bands of SPOT 6 performed better than OLI and were effective for reliably mapping *P. hysterophorus*.

Overall, the results indicate that SPOT 6 had better capabilities in mapping *P. hysterophorus* than OLI. The inferior overall accuracy was due to lower PA resulting from spectral mixing of insignificant *P. hysterophorus* patches and other land cover. In terms of UA, OLI performed better than SPOT 6 due to additional coastal blue and SWIR bands and narrower bandwidths as compared to SPOT 6. Therefore, OLI's spectral configuration was more superior to SPOT 6, and can be used to identify the possible locations of *P. hysterophorus*. Related studies (Pu and

Landry, 2012, Fernandes et al., 2014) found that additional and strategically positioned bands of Worldview-2 improved classification accuracy. SVM classification algorithm showed high effectiveness in discriminating spectral overlaps of *P. hysterophorus* and other land covers that occurred due to relatively broader SPOT 6 spectral bandwidths. ROC curve variable importance from both datasets showed that visible and NIR bands were more important in mapping *P. hysterophorus*. These results are consistent with (Adelabu et al., 2013, Adjorlolo et al., 2013) who indicated that visible and NIR bands show greater discriminatory power in classifying and mapping vegetation species.

3.5.2. Addressing information needs for optimising control mechanisms

The adverse impacts of IAP's such as *P. hysterophorus* on agriculture, biodiversity, human well-being and economy have necessitated investigations into different control and eradication mechanisms and their effectiveness thereof (Strathie et al., 2011, Khan et al., 2012, Kumari and Kohli, 1987). The paucity of spatial information about the distribution and patch sizes of IAP's hinders progress in achieving effective eradication. This study assessed the capability of OLI and SPOT 6 in estimating the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*, valuable for evaluating the effectiveness and optimizing control and eradication mechanisms. The information on distribution and patch sizes is important for environmental research and conservation planning, site specific weed management (SSWM) and for understanding ecosystem diversity and habitat changes as a result of fragmentation by *P. hysterophorus* (Franklin, 2010, Turner et al., 2003, Koller and Lanini, 2005). The distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* were calculated from OLI and SPOT 6 classification maps using FRAGSTATS program.

Results from OLI indicated that approximately 16.22% of the study area is invaded by *P. hysterophorus*, while SPOT 6 indicated that only 6% of the study area is invaded. The discrepancies in the distributions can be attributed to significant differences in spatial resolutions between the OLI and SPOT 6 datasets, i.e. 30m and 6m respectively. Although, minimum mapping unit was the same for both datasets, the subsequent calculations of distribution and patch sizes is a function of the pixel size of each dataset (He et al., 2011). OLI has a lower spatial resolution when compared to SPOT 6, as a result it is expected that SPOT 6 will provide better estimates of the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*. The lower spatial resolution of OLI is inefficient of eliminating gaps inside larger *P. hysterophorus* patches, hence its distribution results may be misleading. In addition, the training data for both datasets were collected from 5m patches, hence greater generalisations can be expected in OLI than in SPOT

6. As a result, the overestimation of the distribution of *P. hysterophorus* was evident from OLI results. On the other hand, the higher spatial resolution of SPOT 6 minimised spectral mixing and detected isolated and insignificant patches. These discrete and insignificant *P. hysterophorus* patches detected by SPOT 6 were removed by post-classification processing (which was more effective in SPOT 6's 6m pixels than 30m pixels of OLI), thus reducing subsequent calculations of distribution and patch metrics.

The higher patch density, i.e. 23.19 per 100 ha in SPOT 6 and lower, i.e. 18.04 per 100 ha in OLI is a result of the observed higher number of patches (NumPatches). With respect to capabilities of the two datasets, the results demonstrated that SPOT 6's spatial resolution was more important in mapping of small patches (<0.5ha) and better delineation of patch boundaries as compared to OLI. A similar study by (Fernandes et al., 2014) found that Worldview-2's spatial resolution was unable to capture the boundaries of *Arundo donax L.* (Giant reed) in detail when compared to airborne data. The capability to delineate boundaries and eliminate gaps inside larger patches is desired for accurate estimation of patch sizes, since existing patches will likely take advantage of available gaps in the landscape for their establishment and proliferation (Malahlela et al., 2014). For invasion ecology, the results imply landscape fragmentation and habitat loss as a result of *P. hysterophorus* invasion which possibly led to a replacement of native species.

Patch size is the single most important information contained in the landscape (McGarigal et al., 2002). An understanding of patch sizes will assist land managers to monitor changes in the landscape and establish relationships between the invader and changes in the ecosystem and habitats (Turner et al., 2003). Detailed visual assessment of *P. hysterophorus* maps from OLI and SPOT 6 indicated that larger patches dominantly occur in communal croplands (Figure 11), while smaller patches occur along roadsides and building peripheries. In essence, the LPI found for both OLI, i.e. 0.26% and SPOT 6, i.e. 0.15% resulted from *P. hysterophorus* invasion in cropland and overgrazed rangelands. Invasion, colonization and establishment of *P. hysterophorus* in the study area can be attributed to landscape and habitat disturbance due to human travel corridors, development of settlements and farming practices. The largest patches in the landscape indicate successful colonization by *P. hysterophorus*, thus the results from OLI imply greater establishment and dominance of the species than those from SPOT 6. Such largest patches in the landscape, usually occurring in croplands and overgrazed grassland, imply a decrease in productivity and extent of communal agricultural lands and appropriates the opportunity of overgrazed lands to recover. On the other hand, patch sizes results (Figure 10)

indicated that most patches calculated from both OLI and SPOT 6 were less than 15 ha. Smaller patches demonstrate new introductions, thus it may be beneficial to target such patches for control and eradication purposes. On the other hand, larger patches can be targeted for containment to prevent further spread. In consistency with the marked differences, i.e. 10.22% observed in the distributions of the *P. hysterophorus* calculated from OLI and SPOT 6. Mann-Whiney U test indicated that there is significant differences in patch sizes calculated from the two datasets at $P < 0.05$. The differences emanates from overestimations by OLI pixels.

Figure 11. SPOT 6 patch sizes in communal croplands overlaid on aerial image acquired in 2009/10 and picture on the right represents the respective infested areas as seen in the field in February 2014.

Overall, the distribution and patch sizes from OLI were higher than those calculated from SPOT 6. Both datasets demonstrate a potential in providing essential information for control and management of *P. hysterophorus*. OLI's relatively larger pixels would be suitable for characterizing well-established, larger patches occurring in croplands and overgrazed rangelands useful for large scale detection and monitoring. As a result, the distribution and patch sizes calculated from OLI for small patches may be misleading. On the other hand, SPOT 6 is suitable for delineating gaps and boundaries of smaller patches useful for site-specific weed management.

3.6. Conclusions

This chapter evaluated the capability of medium resolution multispectral data from Landsat 8 OLI and relatively high resolution SPOT 6 for reliably mapping the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* using SVM classifier. In conclusion, OLI's comprehensive spectral sampling from 430nm to 2290nm, spectral resolution, and number of bands were important for reliably separating *P. hysterophorus* and other land cover types. However, spectral mixing due to larger pixel size limited its capability (i.e. inferior overall accuracy) to provide reliable distribution and patch sizes information. In addition, OLI's larger pixels resulted in overestimations of the distributions and patch sizes, hence may be suitable for mapping well-established patches for large scale monitoring. Although this study did not compare algorithms, SVM showed effectiveness in discriminating spectral overlaps of *P. hysterophorus* and other land covers within SPOT 6 bands. On the other hand, SPOT 6's 6m resolution showed better estimations of distributions and delineating gaps and boundaries in *P. hysterophorus* patches. Ecologically, the distribution and patch sizes calculated from OLI and SPOT 6 showed higher fragmentation of the landscape, habitat loss and decrease in productive land due to *P. hysterophorus* invasion. As a result, small patches can be prioritised for eradication, while larger patches can be contained to prevent further spread.

Overall, the study demonstrated the potential of medium resolution data from OLI and relatively high resolution SPOT 6 in providing useful information necessary for effective land management, site specific weed management, and site prioritisation in conservation plans. Therefore this study provide the basis towards an IAP species detection and monitoring system to identify and target both small and large patches for control and eradication.

CHAPTER 4

SYNTHESIS AND CONCLUSION

4.1. Introduction

In the savanna landscapes of northern Kwa Zulu Natal, *P. hysterophorus* has reached epidemic proportions, thus posing a threat to biodiversity, agriculture, ecosystem functioning and services and human well-being. The physiological characteristics of *P. hysterophorus*, in its vegetative and mature growth stages are dominated by creamy-white flowers. These are produced in only four to six weeks after germination, followed by the production of approximately 25 000 easily dispersible seeds per plant (Dogra et al., 2011). The characteristics of *P. hysterophorus* during vegetative and mature growing stages support its prolific spread and sporadic growth, making it extremely difficult to contain and eradicate. As a result, the effectiveness of physical, chemical and biological control mechanisms is increased during the juvenile growing stage (Reddy et al., 2009, Khan et al., 2012). Thus, for early detection and optimization of eradication mechanisms, it becomes essential to explore the potential of hyperspectral and multispectral remote sensing data for discriminating and mapping *P. hysterophorus*. Conventional methods such as field surveys and manual digitising are laborious, time consuming, costly, and inappropriate for large and inaccessible areas.

The results in this study showed the potential of remote sensing for discriminating and mapping a problematic IAP's, *P. hysterophorus*. Specifically, the study demonstrated the capabilities of canopy hyperspectral data in discriminating *P. hysterophorus* against its co-existing species. A novel approach for overcoming Hughes effect and to select relevant combination of spectral bands that improve accuracy has been proposed. The results were significant for understanding the underlying inter-species spectral differences, and identifying optimal bands valuable for operational mapping using airborne and satellite sensors, choosing suitable sensor for mapping and early IAP species detection (Chapter 2). Based on the identified bands, accessible multispectral data were chosen, i.e. OLI and SPOT 6 and the capability for providing the spatial distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* was pursued. The results demonstrated the potential of the spectral and spatial configurations of OLI and SPOT 6 for reliably mapping the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* (Chapter 3). The information about the spatial distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* is critical for identifying new infestations, optimizing control mechanisms, and effective land management and conservation planning.

4.2. Improving classification accuracy through feature subset selection and dimensionality reduction

The inherent high dimensionality characteristic of hyperspectral data has been identified as the major limitation in literature (Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Adjorlolo et al., 2013). Large training samples ($n > 100$ per class) are required in order to obtain better accuracies. However, in reality, it is costly, tedious and time consuming to collect large samples (Adam and Mutanga, 2009). As a result, reliable discrimination of species with hyperspectral data is compromised due to the effect of $n < p$ (Hughes, 1968). Therefore, selection of a smaller subset of bands that capture the properties of the entire dataset has become a prerequisite for computational efficiency and reliable classification accuracy (Zhang and Ma, 2009, Pal and Foody, 2010, Löw et al., 2013).

An innovative hierarchical approach integrating statistical significant tests, inter-band correlation and variable importance, and SVM-RFE was proposed in Chapter 2. In comparison with entire spectral dataset ($n = 1633$) and a combination of 20 best spectral bands selected by SVM-RFEE, the proposed approach showed that a small subset of spectral bands, $n = 10$ was significant for reliable discrimination of *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. In addition, the hierarchical approach systematically reduced dimensionality and collinearity, hence the selected subset can be used with usually preferred conventional classifiers such as Maximum Likelihood. This is because the selected spectral bands retained important discriminative properties of the entire dataset.

Important findings regarding the significance of feature selection and dimensionality reduction in improving classification accuracy (as highlighted in Chapter 2) are:

1. SVM classification training time and accuracy improved when using 10 spectral bands selected by the proposed hierarchical approach, than when using entire spectral dataset and SVM-RFE.
2. The lower SVM classification accuracy with entire spectral data demonstrate the effect of “curse of dimensionality” on SVM performance, hence higher classification accuracy obtained with the hierarchical approach demonstrate the need for feature selection and dimensionality reduction even when using powerful algorithms.

These findings are valuable for operational discrimination and mapping of *P. hysterophorus* in its early growth stage using airborne and satellite hyperspectral sensors, thus may aid effective control and eradication the species.

4.3. Optimal spectral bands for discrimination of *P. hysterothorus*

Canopy hyperspectral data provide an important starting point for in-depth understanding of species spectral properties prior mapping. The differences in reflectance properties between species are a representation of their differences in canopy and leaf biochemical and biophysical properties (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. Canopy and leaf structures and spectral signatures of *P. hysterothorus* (PH), Acacia Trees (AT), Grass species (GS) and Other plant species (OPS).

Inter-species differences in reflectance properties facilitate species discrimination (Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Chun et al., 2011), however, only few and specific spectral bands with high discriminative ability between all species-pairs are desired. An innovative hierarchical approach that integrates statistical filters (Kruskal Wallis ANOVA, Inter-band correlation and AUC-ROC variable importance) and wrapper-based technique (SVM-RFE) was proposed to select a minimum but optimal subset of spectral bands that capture relevant properties of the entire dataset. At each stage of analysis, the useful spectral bands offering greatest capability for discriminating all species-pairs were determined.

Specifically, Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA identified 599 spectral bands in all regions of the electromagnetic spectrum that are statistically significant and have greater separability for *P. hysterothorus* and its co-species. Subsequently, inter-band correlation and variable importance identified 14 spectral bands that are less redundant and have high individual discriminative ability in distinguishing *P. hysterothorus* from its co-species. Up to this stage, the identified spectral bands are essential for operational applications with conventional classifiers such as

Maximum Likelihood. SVM-RFE selected the final and optimal subset of spectral bands ($n = 10$) that consisted of two red-edge bands located at 685nm and 707nm, one NIR band located at 1115nm and seven SWIR bands at 1971nm, 1982nm, 1966nm, 2003nm, 2013nm and 2005nm. The usefulness of red-edge, NIR and SWIR regions for discriminating species has been reported in literature (Schmidt and Skidmore, 2003, Mutanga and Skidmore, 2007, Adam and Mutanga, 2009). In addition, all selected spectral bands (in this study) were different from those selected in other recent studies (see Table 14), reinforcing the assertion that there is no single technique useful for all species types.

Table 14. Previously selected bands for species discrimination separated by broad spectral regions suggested by (Fernandes et al., 2013).

Spectral regions	Reference	Selected band (s)	Species
350 – 449nm (Blue)	This study	0	<i>P. hysterophorus</i>
	(Jia et al., 2011)	405nm, 424nm, 438 nm	<i>Opium poppy</i>
	(Adam and Mutanga, 2009)	0	<i>Cyperus papyrus</i>
450 – 549nm (Green)	This study	0	<i>P. hysterophorus</i>
	(Jia et al., 2011)	468nm, 524nm, 528nm	<i>Opium poppy</i>
	(Adam and Mutanga, 2009)	0	<i>Cyperus papyrus</i>
550 – 649nm (Red)	This study	0	<i>P. hysterophorus</i>
	(Jia et al., 2011)	0	<i>Opium poppy</i>
	(Adam and Mutanga, 2009)	0	<i>Cyperus papyrus</i>
650 – 749nm (Red-edge)	This study	685nm, 707nm	<i>P. hysterophorus</i>
	(Jia et al., 2011)	726nm, 736nm, 746nm,	<i>Opium poppy</i>
	(Adam and Mutanga, 2009)	745nm, 746nm	<i>Cyperus papyrus</i>
750 – 1299nm (NIR)	This study	1115nm	<i>P. hysterophorus</i>
	(Jia et al., 2011)	754nm, 760nm, 982nm, 1207nm, 1220nm	<i>Opium poppy</i>
	(Adam and Mutanga, 2009)	892nm, 932nm, 934nm, 958nm, 961nm, 989nm	<i>Cyperus papyrus</i>
1300 – 2500nm (SWIR)	This study	1971nm, 1982nm, 1990nm, 1966nm, 2003nm, 2013nm, 2005nm	<i>P. hysterophorus</i>
	(Jia et al., 2011)	1974nm, 1689nm	<i>Opium poppy</i>
	(Adam and Mutanga, 2009)	0	<i>Cyperus papyrus</i>

An important finding in Chapter 2 regarding optimal spectral bands for discrimination of *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species was that:

1. The identified fewer spectral bands by the hierarchical approach, $n = 10$ have greatest potential for discriminating *P. hysterophorus* using current and next generation airborne and satellite hyperspectral sensors. Considering the harmful impacts of *P. hysterophorus*, the selected spectral bands can be used as a guidance for choosing

appropriate bands for detection and mapping of the distribution and patches of the species.

4.4. Reliable information for effective management of *P. hysterophorus*

The spectral discrimination analysis in Chapter 2 identified 10 spectral bands for reliably discriminating *P. hysterophorus* and its co-existing species using canopy hyperspectral data. The optimal bands were located in the red edge (685nm, 707nm), NIR (1115nm) and SWIR (1971nm, 1982nm, 1990nm, 1966nm, 2003nm, 2013nm, 2005nm) regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. As part of the analysis (in Chapter 2), inter-band correlation and variable importance identified other important bands located in blue (427nm), green (537nm) and red (562nm) regions. However, the identified bands do not fully coincide with the bands in most accessible multispectral data. In addition, there was no hyperspectral image available that covers the study area. In that regard, in order to address the challenges of the lack of information on the distribution and patch sizes, we assessed the capability of multispectral data from heritage missions, i.e. Landsat and SPOT. The advantage of the data from these missions is that they have long record of data useful for understanding historical spread of IAP species, are sustainable, the datasets are compatible and contain necessary spectral bands for mapping plant species (Adelabu et al., 2013, Adjorlolo et al., 2013). The usefulness of the spatial and spectral configurations of these datasets have never, to the best of our knowledge, been explored. As such, we compared the capability of OLI and SPOT 6 for mapping the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*.

Important findings in the study (Chapter 3) were:

1. The higher spatial resolution in SPOT 6 was useful for better characterization of the distribution and patch sizes, while the spectral configuration in OLI was more important in identifying possible locations infested by *P. hysterophorus*.
2. The landscape and patch metrics calculated from OLI were markedly different from those calculated from SPOT 6 due to differences in resolution. This was due to the inefficiency of OLI's larger pixels in eliminating gaps inside larger *P. hysterophorus* patches, while SPOT 6's relatively smaller pixels minimised spectral mixing, and detected isolated and insignificant patches.

Results from this study (Chapter 3) provide a basis for understanding the ecological relationships between invasion of *P. hysterophorus* and changes in ecosystems and habitats (Turner et al., 2003). The capability to eliminate gaps by SPOT 6 is desirable since the existing *P.*

hysterophorus patches will likely target such gaps in the landscape for their establishment and proliferation (Malahlela et al., 2014). In addition, landscape and patch metrics from both datasets suggests intense fragmentation and habitat loss as a result of *P. hysterophorus* invasion. Therefore, these findings are critical for allocation of resources for controlling and eradicating *P. hysterophorus* and effective land management and conservation planning (see Appendix B)

4.5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The aim of this study was to evaluate the capability of hyperspectral and multispectral data for mapping problematic IAP's, *P. hysterophorus* in the northern Kwa Zulu Natal province, South Africa. It is clear from the findings in this dissertation that canopy hyperspectral data was useful in identifying optimal spectral bands from highly dimensional data for discriminating *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species. In addition, the findings determined the potential of widely accessible multispectral data from heritage missions (i.e. Landsat and SPOT) for addressing the lack of information about the spatial distributions and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*. Up-to-date and accurate information about the distribution and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus* is critical for understanding its spatial and structural variability in the landscape. Also, the distribution and patch sizes maps may aid proper planning and allocation of resources, hence useful for site-specific weed management.

The overall conclusions based on the objectives of this study as addressed in Chapter 2 and 3 are as follows:

1. There is no single technique that has been proven superior in reducing dimensionality in hyperspectral data (Yang et al., 2005) and identifying smaller subset of bands that capture properties of the entire dataset (Adam and Mutanga, 2009, Pal and Foody, 2010, Jia et al., 2011). The potential of an innovative hierarchical approach that integrates statistical analysis and wrapper-based approach has been demonstrated. Ten hierarchically selected spectral bands had better performance in classifying *P. hysterophorus* and co-existing species when compared to entire spectral dataset and a combination of 20 spectral bands selected by SVM-RFE.
2. In consistency with previous studies (Zhang and Ma, 2009, Pal and Foody, 2010), this study found that SVM classifier was affected by Hughes effect when applied to entire spectral dataset.
3. Previous studies observed that SVM-RFE performs better when feature space is limited <12 bands (Zhang and Ma, 2009, Pal and Foody, 2010). Statistical filters prior to SVM-

RFE were useful for identifying bands with high statistical separability and importance ($n = 14$), hence optimized its performance when applied within the Hierarchical approach.

4. The higher spatial resolution of SPOT 6 offer the potential to provide up-to-date and accurate information on spatial distributions and patch sizes of *P. hysterophorus*, valuable for eradication resource allocation, effective land management and conservation planning.
5. On the other hand, OLI's comprehensive spectral sampling from 430nm – 2291nm, relatively higher spectral resolution and band positioning can be used for locating larger patches of *P. hysterophorus*, valuable for areas where the species is widely spread.

The major limitations of the study emanated from the lower quality of training data, hence resulted in lower classification accuracy for OLI. As such, future studies should focus on improving the quality of training and validation data, and explore the utility of vegetation indices in addition to bands in mapping *P. hysterophorus*. Since OLI offered better spectral configuration and SPOT 6 better spatial configuration, the two datasets can be combined in multiresolution or multiscale classification model to produce higher classification accuracy and better elimination of gaps and well-defined patch boundaries. Also, up-scaling to space-borne hyperspectral data based on the future sensors such as EnMap, should be explored.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Spectral data collection - Field Notes sheet

General Info.

Plot No: _____ Lat: _____

Date: _____ Long: _____

Time: _____ Photo: _____

Operator: _____ Voice: _____

Others: _____

Environmental Info.

LU Type: _____ Slope: _____

Soil Type: _____ Aspect: _____

Soil Moisture: _____ Geology: _____

Vegetation Info. (> 30% cover)

Spp 1: *P. hysterophorus* % Cover: _____ Phenology: _____

Spp 2: _____ % Cover: _____ Phenology: _____

Spp 3: _____ % Cover: _____ Phenology: _____

Spectrometer Readings

Lens: 25⁰ Date: _____ Solar Azimuth: _____

of Scans averaged per scan: 10

Sensor Height above Target/FOV: 0.5m

Scan #	Target	Time	Sky	Solar Z	Sensor A	Sensor Z	FOV	Comments

Comments _____

Appendix 3. Personal communications

Panel 1: Information need.

From: Ian Rushworth <Ian.Rushworth@kznwildlife.com>
Sent: 31 March 2014 03:00 PM
To: Mahlatse Kganyago
Cc: Andrew McConnachie; Michael Braack; Boyd Escott; Clement Adjorlolo; Moses Chimbari; Rob Slotow
Subject: Re: Request for assistance in choosing the study area
Attachments: Parthenium in Maputaland 2014_Richard.pdf

Hi Mahlatse

It would be fantastic if you could get a project going on mapping/detecting Parthenium using RS. We really do need a mechanism of monitoring this species at a landscape scale, including across international borders.

I would gladly assist you in selecting study sites, and have attached some low level aerial photographs indicating the relative ease of detecting this species when it is in dense clusters and in flower. However, would be better to chat on the phone.

I have copied Michael Braack who is the provincial coordination of the KZN Parthenium Management Strategy.

I left a message on your phone earlier.

Regards
Ian

Ian Rushworth, M.Sc.
Manager Biodiversity Research & Assessment Scientific Services Ezemvelo KZN Wildlife PO Box 13053 Cascades 3202

Panel 2: The impact of distribution maps.

From: Ian Rushworth <Ian.Rushworth@kznwildlife.com>
Sent: 26 September 2015 07:54 AM
To: Mahlatse Kganyago
Subject: RE: Parthenium Hectares

Hi Mahlatse

This is awesome, thank you!! What you have achieved is truly ground breaking and will go a long way towards effective management of this alien invasive species. I will download the data as soon as I get into the office.

In terms of the data agreement, please could you send me an electronic copy of the SANSA logo so that we can use it for acknowledgement purposes.

Best wishes

Ian

Ian Rushworth, M.Sc.
Manager Ecological Advice West
Scientific Services
Ezemvelo KZN Wildlife